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Final Study Report

**Impact of EU label changes and revised pregnancy prevention
programme for medicinal products containing valproate:
utilisation and prescribing trends**

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Summary information

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Active substance	Valproic acid (ATC N03AG01, including valproate semisodium and sodium valproate), Valpromide (ATC N03AG02)
Medicinal product	Valproic acid (ATC N03AG01, including valproate semisodium and sodium valproate), Valpromide (ATC N03AG02)
Product reference	Not applicable
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Research question and objectives	<p>This report describes a pharmacoepidemiological study using longitudinal data collected in five electronic health care databases from four EU countries and the UK to investigate the use of valproate-containing medicinal products authorised in the EU before and after implementation of the 2018 revised risk minimisation measures for pregnancy prevention in clinical practice, and effectiveness of the 2018 intervention. The research objectives were:</p> <p>Objective 1: To determine drug utilisation and prescription patterns of valproate-containing medicinal products in females of childbearing potential, and to investigate whether significant changes in prescribing patterns occurred (pre-/post-intervention).</p> <p>Objective 2: To determine prescribers' compliance with the recommendations in the SmPC for valproate-containing medicinal products, by indication, age group, duration of use, and database.</p> <p>Objective 3: To determine, in so far as is possible, patients' use of effective contraception in compliance with recommendations in the SmPC for valproate-containing medicinal products, by indication, age group, method of contraception and database.</p> <p>Objective 4: To determine drug utilisation and prescription patterns over time for alternative medicines prescribed in females of childbearing potential and female becoming pregnant where valproate-containing medicinal products had previously been prescribed or discontinued, by indication, age group and database.</p> <p>Objective 5: Based on the results of the above, to estimate the effectiveness of the 2018 risk minimisation measures for valproates.</p>
Countries of study	Denmark, Italy, the Netherlands, Spain, and United Kingdom.
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Marketing authorisation holder(s)	Not applicable

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1. Abstract

Title

Impact of EU label changes and revised pregnancy prevention programme for medicinal products containing valproate: utilisation and prescribing trends

Keywords

Sodium valproate, congenital abnormalities, contraceptive agents, pregnancy, risk minimisation measures (RMMs), bipolar disorder, epilepsy, migraine prophylaxis.

Rationale and background

In March 2018, the European risk minimisation measures (RMMs) with a Pregnancy Prevention Program (PPP) for valproate-containing medicines was updated. A pharmacoepidemiological study was conducted using longitudinal data collected in five electronic health care databases from four EU countries and the UK to investigate the use of valproates authorised in the EU before and after implementation of the 2018 revised measures for pregnancy prevention in clinical practice, and effectiveness of the 2018 intervention.

Objectives

Objective 1: To determine drug utilisation and prescription patterns of valproate-containing medicinal products in females of childbearing potential, and to investigate whether significant changes in prescribing patterns occurred (pre-/post-intervention).

Objective 2: To determine prescribers' compliance with the recommendations in the Summary of Products Characteristics (SmPC) for valproate-containing medicinal products, by indication, age group, duration of use, and database.

Objective 3: To determine patients' use of effective contraception in compliance with recommendations in the SmPC for valproate-containing medicinal products, by indication, age group, method of contraception, and database.

Objective 4: To determine drug utilisation and prescription patterns over time for alternative medicines prescribed in women who became pregnant, where valproate-containing medicinal products had previously been prescribed or discontinued, by indication, by age group and by database.

Objective 5: Based on the results of the above, to estimate the effectiveness of the 2018 RMMs for valproates.

1.1 Abstract Objective 1

Aim: To determine drug utilisation and prescription patterns of valproates in women of childbearing potential, and to investigate whether significant changes in prescribing patterns after the 2018 EU RMMs occurred, using longitudinal data collected from five electronic health care databases from four EU countries and the UK.

Methods: We performed an observational times series study including all female subjects of childbearing age (aged 12 to 55 years) from the corresponding databases in Denmark (Danish National Registers, DNR), Italy (ARS Tuscany), the Netherlands (PHARMO Database Network), Spain (Base de datos para la Investigación Farmacoepidemiológica en Atención Primaria, BIFAP), and UK

(Clinical Practice Research Datalink, CPRD) between 01 January 2010 to 31 December 2020. The incident use, prevalent use and rate of discontinuation thereof was estimated per month in each data source, in addition to the change in level and trend in use after the implementation of the 2018 EU RMMs, using an interrupted time series (ITS) analysis design.

Results: There were 69,533 valproate users out of a total of 9,699,371 female subjects of childbearing age from the five participating centres during the study period. The median follow-up time of the study population ranged between 3.5-10.0 years and the mean age at the start of follow-up was always ≥ 30 years in different centres. The monthly incidence rate of valproate use ranged between 0.01-0.47 per 1000 persons months across databases and the prevalence rate ranged between 1.2-7.7 per 1000 female subjects. While the observed rates were similar for DNR, PHARMO, BIFAP and CPRD, the rates of prevalent use were much higher in ARS Tuscany. We observed a statistically significant declining trend in prevalent use of valproates in all countries/regions, for which an ITS analysis could be performed, but no significant decreasing trend in incidence rates after the 2018 RMMs compared to the period before. The monthly rate of valproate discontinuers ranged between 1-8% across all databases, and in no database we observed a significant increase in trend or level of valproate discontinuation after the 2018 intervention compared to time prior.

Conclusion: We observed declining trends in prevalent use of valproates after the 2018 RMMs across all databases. However, there were no declining trends in incidence rate of valproates in none of databases. The rate of discontinuation of valproates was not affected by the 2018 RMMs.

1.2 Abstract Objective 2

Aim: To determine prescribers' compliance with the recommendations in the SmPC for valproates (sections 4.4, 4.6), in form of prescribing pregnancy tests or contraceptive coverage before a treatment episode with valproates, using longitudinal data collected from five electronic health care databases from four EU countries and the UK.

Methods: We performed an observational times series study including all female subjects of childbearing age (aged 12 to 55 years) who used valproates from the corresponding databases in Denmark (DNR), Italy (ARS Tuscany), the Netherlands (PHARMO Database Network), Spain (BIFAP), and UK (CPRD) between 01 January 2010 to 31 December 2020. First, we separately estimated the proportion of valproate users with a record of a pregnancy test within the 90 days i) before and ii) after the date of valproate prescribing or dispensing per month. We estimated the change in level and trend in these proportions after the implementation of the 2018 EU RMMs. Second, we estimated the proportion of valproate users with a record of contraceptive (prescribed or dispensed with a prescription, or identified through medical events or procedures records) in 90-days before the prescription, or prescribed/dispensed during a contraceptive episode. We then estimated the change in level and trend in this proportion after the implementation of the 2018 EU intervention, using an ITS analysis design.

Results: We included 69,533 female valproate users from the five participating centres during the study period, with a median follow-up time between 4.4-11.0 years and the mean age at the start of follow-up ≥ 34 years. Due to the limited data on pregnancy tests from all databases, modelling of any trend change in proportion of valproate prescriptions or dispensings with an adherent pregnancy test before versus after 2018 RMMs was not possible. The rate of recorded contraceptive coverage at the start of valproate treatment was low across all centres, as only 0.5-23% of valproate prescriptions/dispensings each month were accompanied by a contraceptive prescription in 90-days before, and only between 0.5-25% of new valproate treatment episode had started during contraceptive use. There was no increasing trend in compliant valproate prescriptions/ dispensings with a contraceptive coverage after the 2018 RMMs across the studied databases, and the only increase in level was observed in PHARMO.

Conclusion: We found in general low rates of recorded adherent contraceptive coverage with valproate use across all studied regions/countries, and there was no increased trend in compliant

valproate prescriptions/dispensings with a contraceptive coverage after the 2018 RMMs compared to time prior. Due to limited data availability, rates of adherent pregnancy tests and the trend change after the intervention could not be studied.

1.3 Abstract Objective 3

Aim: To determine patients' use of effective contraception in compliance with recommendations in the SmPC for valproates (sections 4.4, 4.6), in form of the overall outcome of pregnancy events, using longitudinal data collected from five electronic health care databases from four EU countries and the UK.

Methods: We performed an observational times series study including all female subjects of childbearing age (aged 12 to 55 years) who used valproates from the corresponding databases in Denmark (DNR), Italy (ARS Tuscany), the Netherlands (PHARMO Database Network), Spain (BIFAP), and UK (CPRD) between 01 January 2010 to 31 December 2020. We estimated the incidence of new pregnancies during a period of valproate use per month and the change in level and trend in this rate after the implementation of the 2018 EU intervention, using an ITS analysis design.

Results: We included 69,533 female valproate users from the five participating centres during study period, with a median follow-up time between 4.4-11.0 years and the mean age at the start of follow-up ≥ 34 years. In general, we observed a substantial number of concurrent new valproate prescriptions/dispensings during a pregnancy time window in ARS Tuscany (386 pre- and 40 post 2018 intervention), BIFAP (330 pre and 20 post) and CPRD (204 pre and 56 post), while there were fewer concurrent events in PHARMO (27 pre and 0 post). However, the rates of concurrent events declined for most databases after the 2018 intervention. There was no data on pregnancy counts available from DNR.

Conclusion: Despite the declining rates after the 2018 intervention, high counts and rates of concurrent pregnancy events with a valproate prescription/dispensing were observed across most studied countries/regions.

1.4 Abstract Objective 4

Aim: To determine drug utilisation and prescription patterns over time for alternative medications prescribed in women of childbearing potential and pregnant women where valproates had previously been prescribed or discontinued, using longitudinal data collected from five electronic health care databases from four EU countries and the UK.

Methods: We performed an observational times series study including all female subjects of childbearing age (aged 12 to 55 years) who used valproates from the corresponding databases in Denmark (DNR), Italy (ARS Tuscany), the Netherlands (PHARMO Database Network), Spain (BIFAP), and UK (CPRD) between 01 January 2010 to 31 December 2020. We estimated the rates of alternative medication prescriptions/dispensings for the indications epilepsy, bipolar disorder, and migraine among valproate users and the rate of switching from valproate to an alternative medicine per month. Then, the change in trend of switches from valproate to alternative medications before and after the implementation of the 2018 EU intervention was estimated, using an ITS analysis design.

Results: We included 69,533 female valproate users from the five participating centres during study period, with a median follow-up time between 4.4-11.0 years and the mean age at the start of follow-up ≥ 34 years. We found an increasing trend in rates of alternative medicine use for epilepsy and bipolar diseases indications of valproates across the study period in most databases (i.e., DNR, ARS Tuscany, PHARMO and CPRD), while the rates for migraine were mostly steady. The monthly rate of switch from a valproate to an alternative medication was similar across all DAPs and ranged

between 1-8%. Running an ITS analysis was not possible for most of the included databases due to the low frequency of switching, but there was a significant increase in trend in switching rates from valproates to alternative medicine after the 2018 RMMs in ARS Tuscany.

Conclusion: Although the trend in alternative medication use for most indications of valproates (epilepsy and bipolar disorder) was increasing during the study period, the only significant increase in trend in switching rates from valproates to alternative medications after the 2018 RMMs was observed in ARS Tuscany.

1.5 Abstract Objective 5

Aim: To draw conclusions on the effectiveness of the 2018 EU RMMs for valproates.

Methods: Evidence generated from Objectives 1-4, weighed by the strengths and limitations of the analyses, was used to draw conclusions on the effectiveness of the RMMs, per country and across European countries included in the study.

Results: We found a generally declining trend in prevalence rate of valproate use after the 2018 RMMs in almost all databases (Objective 1), but also no increasing trend in compliant valproate prescriptions/dispensings with a contraceptive coverage (Objective 2). There was a substantial number of occurrences of pregnancy events (as the final endpoint) concurrently with valproate exposure across most included databases, but the rates declined after 2018 (Objective 3). Furthermore, we observed a significant increase in switching rates from valproates to alternative medications only in few regions (such as ARS Tuscany) (Objective 4). Noteworthy, these findings should be interpreted in context of the limitations that we faced, such as an inability to investigate some objectives due to limited data availability on pregnancy test or over-the-counter use of some contraceptives, and the occurrence of COVID-19 pandemic, which has shortened and impacted our post-intervention period and limited our ability to run ITS analyses for some objectives and some databases.

Conclusion: Based on the findings on various objectives in this study, we can conclude that there was a small impact of the 2018 RMMs on valproate use and prescribing in the studied European countries/regions. Considering the limitations of this study (such as not studying all PPP elements, the included databases had important limitations, and the study period after 2018 intervention was rather short), the results of other currently ongoing studies are needed to have a clearer picture of the appropriate implementation of 2018 RMMs on valproate use in Europe.

2. Abbreviations

ADR – Adverse drug reaction

AEMPS - Agencia Espanola de Medicamentos y Productos Sanitarios, Madrid, Spain

ARS - Agenzia Regionale di Sanità della Toscana, Italy

BIFAP - Base de datos para la Investigación Farmacoepidemiológica en Atención Primaria

CDM – Common Data Model

CMDh - The Coordination Group for Mutual Recognition and Decentralised Procedures - Human

CPRD – Clinical Practice Research Datalink

DAP – Data Access Partner

DHPC - Direct Healthcare Professional Communication

DNR – Danish National Registers

EMA – European Medicines Agency

EU – European Union

FICF - Fundació Institut Català de Farmacologia, Barcelona, Spain

IQR – Interquartile Range

ITSA – Interrupted Time Series Analysis

LSHTM – London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine, UK

PHARMO – The PHARMO Database Network, The Netherlands

PI – Principal Investigator

PPP – Pregnancy Prevention Programme

PRAC - The Pharmacovigilance Risk Assessment Committee

RMM – Risk Minimisation Measures

SmPC – Summary of Product Characteristics

UMCU – University Medical Center Utrecht, the Netherlands

UU – Utrecht University, the Netherlands

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4. Other responsible parties

Name	Role
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5. Milestones

Milestone	Planned date	Actual date	Comments
Preliminary study plan	25 Apr 2019		
Study protocol	12 Jul 2019		
Start of data collection	July 2020		The month in which data extraction for some centres started. Data collection is a part of routine practice (clinical, administrative, surveillance), and has been ongoing since before 2010 in all data sources.
End of data collection	September 2020	December 2020	The month in which data extraction for some centres ended.
Study report	25 December 2021	25 March 2022	Extension was granted. Analysis of the full DNR data, as stated in the original protocol (V1.0) was not possible due to delayed data access.
Manuscript	25 February 2022	11 May 2022	Extension was granted. Analysis of the full DNR data, as stated in the original protocol (V1.0) was not possible due to delayed data access.

6. Rationale and background

Valproic acid as 2-propylpentanoic acid is a broad-spectrum antiseizure medication, first introduced in Europe in the 1960s. Valproate and the related substances (i.e., valproic acid, sodium valproate, magnesium valproate, valproate semisodium and valpromide) are licensed for the treatment of epilepsy and acute mania in patients with bipolar disorder in Europe, and as prophylaxis for bipolar disorders and migraine headaches in some EU Member States.

The teratogenic risk of congenital malformations and neurodevelopmental disorders associated with the use of valproates in pregnant women is well established. Valproates are considered as the most teratogenic antiseizure medication.^{1,2} Previous studies showed that >10% of children exposed to valproates in utero had some kind of congenital malformations, and between 30-40% of children exposed in utero showed degrees of neurodevelopmental or behavioural disorders at an older age.^{3,4} This includes a higher risk of cognitive deficits, such as a reduction of 7-10 points in IQ, a decline in verbal and memory abilities, and a predisposition to develop behavioural abnormalities such as autistic spectrum disorder and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder.^{3,4,5} The risk is dose dependent without any safe threshold below which no risk exists.⁶

Following the accumulated evidence on risks and hazards of using valproates during pregnancy regarding congenital anomalies and various developmental disorders for the neonates, the European Medicines Agency (EMA) announced recommendations and some risk minimisation measures (RMMs) in 2014 to warn against valproate use in all women of childbearing age, especially during pregnancy.⁷ The RMMs included a set of educational materials and Direct Healthcare Professional Communication (DHPC) to raise the understanding and awareness of prescribers and patients on the risks associated with valproates during pregnancy. According to these, valproates should not be used to treat epilepsy in female children, pregnant women and women of childbearing potential unless alternative treatments are ineffective or not tolerated; manic episodes in bipolar disorder should only be treated with valproate when lithium is contraindicated or not tolerated, and the prophylaxis of migraine attacks has been contraindicated in pregnancy and women of childbearing potential not using effective methods of contraception. Moreover, educational materials, warnings and precautions with updated information on the risks related to exposure during pregnancy were included in the product information of all medicinal products containing valproates, to better inform the healthcare professionals and women.⁷

A cross-sectional survey among physicians that evaluated the effectiveness of the 2014 RMMs across France, Germany, Spain, Sweden and United Kingdom concluded that a majority of physicians had good knowledge about prescribing valproates in women of childbearing age.⁸ However, a review by the EMA's Pharmacovigilance Risk Assessment Committee (PRAC) in 2018 showed that despite the 2014 RMMs many patients were still not informed on the risks of using valproates during pregnancy, a high level of exposure to sodium divalproate and valpromide among women of childbearing potential persisted and that prescribing conditions were not adhered to, especially in the bipolar disorder indication.⁹ Following this and in March 2018, a referral procedure ([EMEA/H/A-31/1454](#)) under Article 31 of Directive 2001/83/EC resulting from pharmacovigilance data confirmed the already known teratogenic risk and neurodevelopmental disorders associated with the use of valproate and related substances in pregnant women. The PRAC noted insufficient adherence to the educational measures for patients and healthcare professionals introduced in 2014 which did not reach the targeted audience in a satisfactory rate and usage data indicated that valproate is still used by a considerable proportion of women of childbearing potential for both epilepsy and bipolar disorder indications.¹⁰ The Coordination Group for Mutual Recognition and Decentralised Procedures - Human (CMDh) agreed with PRAC's recommendations, and this position was later agreed by a majority vote in the European Commission, which issued a legally binding decision valid across the continent.¹⁰

The core of the new recommendations and measures of the PRAC in 2018, endorsed by CMDh and the European Commission, was introducing a special "pregnancy prevention programme (PPP)".¹⁰ It

includes a set of measures to strengthen the 2014 RMMs and to make sure that valproates are not used in a pregnant woman. This includes an assessment of each patient's potential to become pregnant, pregnancy tests before starting and during treatment with valproates, counselling about the risks of valproate treatment and the need for effective contraception throughout treatment, and an annual review of ongoing treatment by a specialist using a new risk acknowledgement form. Furthermore, changes to the product information (package leaflet for patients and Summary of Product Information (SmPC) for healthcare professionals) including a visual warning on medications boxes were foreseen. The educational materials with updated information for patients and doctors and "patient alert card" was introduced to more efficiently warn patients of the risks associated by using valproates.

According to the 2018 measures by PRAC, valproates are contraindicated in women of childbearing potential for all indications (epilepsy, bipolar disorders and prophylaxis of migraine attacks) unless the conditions of a PPP, which has to be implemented in all EU Member States, are fulfilled. Valproate treatment was contraindicated during pregnancy for the indication bipolar disorders and prophylaxis of migraine attacks, and for the indication epilepsy unless there are no suitable treatment alternatives. In addition, valproate treatment should only be initiated and supervised by a specialist in the management of epilepsy, including annual treatment reviews and should only be prescribed as monotherapy and at the lowest effective dose. In section 4.6 of the SmPC new recommendations were included in case of pregnancy and pregnancy planning that require specialist consultation on switching to alternative treatment options prior to conception, and before contraception is discontinued, or discontinuation of valproate treatment.

PRAC also imposed post-authorisation safety studies (PASS) to assess risk minimisation effectiveness, including prescribing and switching patterns in clinical practice and patient and healthcare professional awareness of the PPP and revised educational materials. This study is complementary to the studies imposed on marketing authorisation holders of medicines containing valproate and related substances.

This study has been developed under the Framework service contract (nr. EMA/2018/28/PE) with regard to the re-opening of competition no 2. The objective of this study was to investigate the use of valproate-containing medicinal products authorised in the EU before and after implementation of the 2018 revised measures for pregnancy prevention in clinical practice, and effectiveness of the 2018 intervention, using longitudinal data collected in five electronic health care databases from four EU countries and the UK. This study has been registered in the EU PAS register (EUPAS31001).

7. Research question and objectives

The main research question of this study was, "What was the effect of the EU label changes and the revised pregnancy prevention programme (2018) on utilisation of valproate-containing medicinal products and to what extent did prescribers and patients comply with recommendations?". To answer this, we completed the following objectives:

Objective 1. To determine drug utilisation and prescription patterns of valproate-containing medicinal products (ATC codes: N03AG01, N03AG02) in females of childbearing potential, and to investigate whether significant changes in prescribing patterns occurred (pre-/post-intervention). This included an investigation into: a) incidence and prevalence rates of valproate use, stratified by age groups, indication (i.e., epilepsy, bipolar disorder, and migraine prophylaxis), dose, duration of use, per each country (database); b) discontinuation rates of valproates by age group, indication, reason for discontinuation (i.e., pregnancy wish, pregnancy, adverse drug reactions, other), duration of use, per each country (database).

Objective 2. To determine prescribers' compliance with the recommendations in the SmPC (sections 4.2, 4.3, 4.4 and 4.6) in form of prescription of pregnancy tests and contraceptive coverage for valproate-containing medicinal products, by indication (i.e., epilepsy, bipolar disorder and migraine prophylaxis), age group, dose, duration of use, method of contraception, per each country (database).

Objective 3. To determine, in so far as is possible, patients' compliance with recommendations in the SmPC for valproate-containing medicinal products in form of the occurrence of concurrent pregnancy events with valproate use, by indication (i.e., epilepsy, bipolar disorder and migraine prophylaxis), age group, per each country (database).

Objective 4. To determine drug utilisation and prescription patterns over time for alternative medications prescribed in females of childbearing potential and female becoming pregnant where valproate-containing medicinal products had previously been prescribed or discontinued, by indication, age group, per each country (database).

Objective 5. Based on the results of the above, to estimate the effectiveness of the 2018 EU RMMs for valproates. This included a synthesis of results in terms of: a) Appropriate use of medicinal products containing valproate and related substances in females of childbearing potential in line with SmPC recommendations; b) Appropriate use of pregnancy testing prior to treatment initiation, during treatment and after stopping treatment; c) Use of effective contraception in females of childbearing potential exposed to valproate and related substances; d) Incidence of pregnancies in females of childbearing potential exposed to valproate and related substances.

8. Amendments and updates to the report

Date	Amendment	Justification	Report section

9. Research methods

9.1. Study design

The design for the different objectives was a cross-sectional time series study, where outcomes (drug utilisation, pregnancy prevention measures, pregnancy) were assessed every month. An interrupted time series (ITS) analysis has been conducted for hypothesis testing. The full study protocol can be found in **Annex 2**.

9.2. Setting and data sources

Data from five sources were included: Netherlands (sample, nationally representative), Denmark (nationwide), Italy (regional database, Tuscany), Spain (multiple regions), and United Kingdom (sample, nationally representative), covering more than 30 million source population (approximate estimate: 15-20 million childbearing age females). **Table 1** presents an overview of the included databases.

Table 1. Overview of databases used in this study.

Characteristic	DNR*	ARS Tuscany	PHARMO Nationally representative	BIFAP Multi-regional	CPRD (HES-linked) Nationally representative
Handling partner	UCPH	ARS	PHARMO	AEMPS	LSHTM
Country (population size, millions)	Denmark (5.8)	Italy (59.8)	Netherlands (17.1)	Spain (46.5)	UK (66)
Type of database	ADM	ADM	EMR	EMR	EMR
No. active patients in database, millions	5.8	3.6	4.2 (prior to linkage)	9	10.0
Date in	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Date out	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Updates	Annual	Monthly	Annual	Annual	6 monthly
GP Rx	Yes (no prescription data)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Outpatient Rx	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
Private Rx	Yes	No	No	No	No
Inpatient hospital Rx	No	No	Yes (not used here)	No	No
Date of Rx	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Quantity of Rx	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Duration of Rx	Yes	Based on DDD	Yes	Yes	Yes
Daily dose	Yes	Based on DDD	Yes	Yes	Yes
Brand/generic	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Registered diagnosis compatible with indication of valproate	Diagnosis codes in history	Diagnosis codes in history	Diagnosis codes in history	Linked to prescription and diagnosis codes in medical history	Read diagnosis as a proxy
Coding of drugs	ATC	ATC	ATC	ATC	Gemscript/BNF product codes

Dosing regimen	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes (incomplete)
Pregnancy testing	No	No	No (mainly OTC)	Yes	Yes
Pregnancy prevention					
Oral contraceptives	Yes	No	Yes	Yes (only those dispensed with a prescription)	Yes
Duration OC	Yes (based on DDDs)	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Intrauterine device/system					
Date fitted	Yes (not copper IUD)*	No	Yes	No	Yes
Date removed	No	No	Yes	No	No
Implanon/Nexplanon/etonogestrel					
Date inserted	Date of prescription fill	No	Proxy based on date of prescription fill	Not systematically	Yes
Date removed	No	No	Proxy based on date of prescription fill	Not systematically	No
Noristerat/norethisterone enantate					
Date injected	Not marketed	No	Not marketed	Yes	Yes
Depo-provera					
Date injected	Date of prescription fill	No	Proxy based on date of prescription fill	Yes	Yes
Written record of OC advice	No	No	Free text, if recorded by GP	Free text potentially	Yes (partial)
Hysterectomy	Yes*	Yes	Yes	If recorded by GP	Yes (HES linkage)
Oophorectomy	Yes*	Yes	Yes	If recorded by GP	Yes (HES linkage)
Sterilisation	Yes*	Yes	Yes	If recorded by GP	Yes (HES linkage)
Partner vasectomy	No	No	No	No	No
Completed Menopause	No	No	Free text potentially	If recorded by GP and free text potentially	No
Outcomes					
Reasons for stopping Valproate	No	No	No	Free text potentially	No
Coding of disease	ICD-10*	ICD-9 CM/ICD-10	ICPC, ICD-9, ICD-10	ICPC-2, ICD-9, ICD 10, snomed	CPRD: Read HES: ICD-10 and OPCS-4
Pregnancy outcomes	Linkage to birth register*	Linkage to birth register, hospitalization, mental health registry	Linkage to perinatal registry	From mother's records, if recorded by the GP	Mother-Baby Link via algorithm in CPRD
Number of pregnancies per year	60.000 births/year	Not yet known	29000 linked pregnancies / year	100,000	Not yet known

Abbreviations, ADM: Administrative; ATC: Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical; EMR: Electronic Medical Records; ICD: International Classification of Disease, ICPC: International Classification of Primary Care; DDD: defined daily dose; DNR: Danish national registers.

* Due to data access delays for the DNR, diagnosis, procedure and pregnancy information will not be available during the study; only information on prescriptions will be available

Denmark: Danish National Registries (DNR)

Denmark has a tax-funded health care system ensuring easy and equal access to health care for all its citizens, and all contacts with the system are recorded in administrative and medical registers. The records carry a unique personal identification number, called the CPR-number, assigned to every Danish citizen at birth. Linkage between registers at an individual level is possible because this CPR-number is used in all Danish registers.¹¹ All registers have a nationwide coverage and an almost 100% capture of contacts covering information on currently 5.8 million inhabitants plus historical information. For the purpose of this study information was obtained from the following registries: The Danish National Patient Registry (DNPR) includes all hospitalisation records since 1977, and incorporating all outpatient diagnoses and services also starting from 1995 using the International Classification of Diseases, 10th Revision (ICD-10).¹² The Danish National Prescription Registry includes data on all drugs dispensed from Danish pharmacies from 1995 and onwards, including dispensing date, ATC code, product code and amount.¹³ Sociodemographic data is available from the Danish Civil Registration System, such as sex, date of birth, migration, vital status and civil status recorded since 1968.

Italy: ARS

The Italian National Healthcare System is organised at regional level: the national government sets standards of assistance and a tax-based funding for each region, and regional governments are responsible to provide to all their inhabitants. Tuscany is an Italian region, with around 3.6 million inhabitants. The Agenzia regionale di sanità della Toscana (ARS Tuscany) is a research institute of the Tuscany Region. ARS database comprises all the data that are collected by the Tuscany Region to account for the healthcare delivered to its inhabitants. Moreover, ARS collects data from regional initiatives. The data in the ARS data source can be linked with each other at the individual level, through a pseudonymous identifier. ARS database routinely collects primary care and secondary care prescriptions of drugs for outpatient use, and is able to link them at the individual level with hospital admissions, admissions to emergency care, records of exemptions from co-payment, dispensings of diagnostic tests and procedures, causes of death, mental health services registry. A pathology registry is available, mostly recorded in free text, but with morphology and topographic Snomed codes. Mother-child linkage is possible through the birth registry.

The Netherlands: PHARMO and the Netherlands Perinatal registry

The PHARMO Database Network is a population-based network of electronic healthcare databases (EHDs) and combines data from different primary and secondary healthcare settings in the Netherlands.¹⁵ These different data sources, including data from general practices, in- and out-patient pharmacies, clinical laboratories, hospitals, the cancer registry, pathology registry and perinatal registry, are linked on a patient level through validated algorithms.¹⁶ Detailed information on the methodology and the validation of the used record linkage method can be found elsewhere.¹⁷

The longitudinal nature of the PHARMO Database Network system enables to follow up more than nine million individuals in the Netherlands, which equals to more than half of the Dutch population, with an average follow-up of 12 years in 2018.¹⁵ Data collection period, catchment area and overlap between data sources differ. Therefore, the final cohort size for any study will depend on the data sources included. As data sources are linked on an annual basis, the average lag time of the data is one year. All electronic patient records in the PHARMO Database Network include information on age, sex, socioeconomic status and mortality. Other available information depends on the data source. To address the objectives of the present study the following PHARMO databases were used: General Practitioner Database, Out-patient Pharmacy Database and Pregnancy Register.

The General Practitioner (GP) Database comprises data from electronic patient records registered by GPs. The records include information on diagnoses and symptoms, laboratory test results,

referrals to specialists and healthcare product/ drug prescriptions. The prescription records include information on type of product, prescription date, strength, dosage regimen, quantity and route of administration. Drug prescriptions are coded according to the WHO Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) Classification System.¹⁸ Diagnoses and symptoms are coded according to the International Classification of Primary Care (ICPC), which can be mapped to ICD codes, but can also be entered as free text.

The Out-patient Pharmacy Database comprises GP or specialist prescribed healthcare products dispensed by the out-patient pharmacy. The dispensing records include information on type of product, date, strength, dosage regimen, quantity, route of administration, prescriber specialty and costs. Drug dispensings are coded according to the WHO ATC Classification System. Oral contraceptives are mostly prescribed by GPs, but can also be obtained directly in the pharmacy, this was captured in PHARMO as was proven before.¹⁹ PHARMO is listed under the ENCePP resources database.²⁰

The Netherlands Perinatal Registry (PRN) is maintained by Perined and comprises data on pregnancies, births and neonatal outcomes of births in the Netherlands, voluntarily collected by perinatal caregivers, mainly for benchmarking.²¹ For research purposes the data can be linked with the PHARMO Database Network via a trusted third party. Records include information on mothers (e.g., maternal age, obstetric history, parity), pregnancy (e.g., mode of conception, mode of delivery) and children (e.g., birth weight, gestational age, Apgar score). Diagnoses and symptoms are coded according to the Perinatal Registry code lists. For more information: <https://www.perined.nl>

Permission on a project-basis is needed from PHARMO as well as Perined to obtain these data. Combined Out-patient Pharmacy and PRN data currently cover a catchment area representing 0.5 million residents for the data cut up to 2015. Additional linkages to the other PHARMO databases can be performed on a patient-level. Data collection period, catchment area and overlap between data sources differ. Therefore, the final cohort size for any study will depend on the data sources included.

Spain: BIFAP

BIFAP (Base de Datos para la Investigación Farmacoepidemiológica en Atención Primaria), a computerised database of medical records of primary care (www.bifap.aemps.es) is a non-profit research project funded by the Spanish Agency for Medicines and Medical Devices (AEMPS). The project started in 2001 and currently includes data on 12 million patients with clinical information from 14810 physicians (GPs and paediatricians) from nine participant Autonomous Regions.²² BIFAP database currently includes anonymised clinical and prescription/ dispensing data of around 14 million (9.4 active population) patients representing 85% of the population in participating regions, and 29% of the total Spanish population. Mean duration of follow up in the database is 8.7 years. Information collected by PCPs includes administrative, socio-demographic, lifestyle, and other general data, clinical diagnosis and health problems, results of diagnostic procedures, interventions, and prescriptions/dispensations. Diagnoses are classified according to the International Classification of Primary Care (ICPC)-2, ICD-9CM and SNOMEDCT system, and a variable proportion of clinical information is registered in "medical notes" in free text fields in the EMR. Additionally, information on hospital discharge diagnoses coded in ICD-10 terminology is linked to patients included in BIFAP for a subset of periods and regions participating in the database. All information on prescriptions of medicines by the PCP is incorporated and linked by the PCP to a health problem (episode of care), and information on the dispensing of medicines at pharmacies is extracted from the e-prescription system that is widely implemented in Spain BIFAP. A mother-child linkage has not been made so far and no private/specialist prescribing is available.

United Kingdom: Clinical Practice Research Datalink

The Clinical Practice Research Datalink (CPRD) comprises computerised medical records of general practitioners (GPs) from 1987 onwards. CPRD is one of the world's largest collections of primary care data, sourced from a UK-wide network of over 1,100 primary care practices.²³ CPRD comprises two complementary databases – Gold (from practices with VISION software) and Aurum (from practices with EMIS software). Combined, they include around 10 million currently registered active patients, representative of the UK population, of whom 75% have at least 20 years of follow up. The data covers ~15% of the population. GPs play a gatekeeper role in the UK health care system, as they are responsible for primary health care and specialist referrals. Patients are affiliated to a practice, which centralises the medical information from the GPs, specialist referrals, hospitalisations and tests. The data recorded in the CPRD include demographic information, prescription details, clinical events, preventive care provided, specialist referrals, laboratory results, hospital admissions and death. The validity of a wide range of drug exposure data is routinely tested. Only those practices that meet quality standards are used for research (about 10% of the practices that send data to CPRD do not meet the quality standards). Furthermore, validation studies are conducted regularly by comparing CPRD data to written notes of general practitioners.²⁴ A subset of CPRD records (from practices in England) are linked to the national Hospital Episode Statistics (HES) database. HES is a national dataset containing data on in-patient, out-patient and emergency care from all NHS hospitals in England. Administrative details, information on ICD-10 coded clinical diagnoses and OPCS-4-coded procedures are included. Office for National Statistics (ONS) mortality data recording causes of death from death certificates are collated by ONS and routinely linked to CPRD and HES. Of relevance for this proposal, collaborative work between LSHTM and CPRD researchers has recently established a pregnancy register within the CPRD, identifying instances of pregnancy and pregnancy outcomes since 1987.

9.3. Study population

The study was conducted in women of childbearing age (i.e., 12-55 years) between 01 January 2010 and 31 December 2020 (see **Figure 1**). Women entered the cohort on the latest of the following dates: 01 January 2010 having one year of previous valid data, the twelfth birthday, and database registration. The cohort exit was defined as the earliest of 01 January 2020, the 56th birthday, death, and database deregistration.

Figure 1 – schematic of data coverage and definition of study population

- a. Subjects may be excluded during initial data processing if they meet the general exclusion criteria. This will help to reduce data volume. DAPs may apply these exclusion criteria during their ETL, but they must report this (it will also be detected when assessing at patient flow). Subjects with any record of male sex will be excluded.
- b. Time series of cross-sectional analyses is performed over this period (monthly analyses). The final month will begin December 1st 2020.

9.4. Study variables

Lists of medicine, diagnostic, regional procedure and other medical observation codes, as well as codes generated by processing free text information can be found in **Annex 5**.

9.4.1. Exposure definition

Valproate-containing medical products (Valproic acid, sodium valproate, valproate pivoxil, valproate semisodium, valpromide, valproate bismuth, calcium valproate, valproate magnesium) were the main study exposure.

Operationalisation

Prescriptions or dispensing events were extracted from drug files by ATC/ CPRD product code or product name. A list of nationally authorised products is available in **Annex 2** (sub-annex I).

Treatment episodes were separately constructed for valproate exposure and contraception exposure following existing methodology.²⁵ An episode for a product with a given ATC/ BNF code started on the date of incident prescription/ dispensing. A tailored software package (AdhereR) was used to investigate different periods between prescriptions for definition of discontinuation (30 days and 90 days – see sensitivity analyses below) as well as construction of treatment periods for stratification by prior duration use.²⁶ Each data access partner (DAP) recommended the approach that is expected to minimise exposure misclassification in their database, given their available data. For example, this was based on the number of units prescribed/ dispensed and the dosage regimen (prescribed daily dose), or when information on dosage regimen was missing, based on either the typical period for duration of a prescription for chronic diseases in the country (e.g., 30 or 90 days) or the duration based on the assumption that one defined daily dose (DDD) per day. Details of the DAP-specific choices of algorithms to define treatment duration is reported in **Annex 3**. Overlap between prescription refills of a specific valproate (i.e., a prescription refill with the same ATC/ BNF code is given before the previous prescription runs out) was accounted for by adding the overlapping days to the end of the treatment episode. An upper bound of 30 days was set, so the added overlap could

not exceed this limit. A permissible gap of 30 days between episodes was implemented, so that if there was a gap of less than 30 days between the end of one episode and the next, the episodes were combined and the person was assumed to be exposed during the gap.

Based on the constructed treatment episodes, subjects were counted as prevalent (or current) users of valproate (or contraception) in a month if they had an episode of treatment that overlapped with that month by at least one day, while they were still eligible to be included in the study. A person was counted as an incident (new) user in a specific month if they started a first ever episode of treatment that month since the start of study in January 2010, also considering the 1-year look-back period of 2009.

Discontinuation of valproates was defined as no record of prescription/ dispensing within 90 days following the theoretical end of the last valproate prescription/ dispensing within a valproate episode. An individual was classified as a discontinuer in a specific month if their valproate treatment episode ended within that month and they did not have a record of a valproate prescription or dispensing within the following 90 days. If a person did not have at least 90 days of follow-up after that month, they could not be classified as a discontinuer, and therefore discontinuation was not assessed for the last 3 months of the study period (due to insufficient follow-up). Females meeting criteria for discontinuation may re-initiate, leading to multiple episodes of treatment.

Duration of use

Duration of use was defined as the time from initiation of treatment based upon the first recorded prescription or dispensing in the look-back or study periods until a specific month. Treatment duration per episode was stratified as follows: <6 months, 6 months to <1 year, 1 year or more.

Dose

Dose information was extracted as recorded in each database. Due to a lack of availability of information on plasma concentration levels of valproate and heterogeneity in the testing of blood plasma between clinicians and countries, where available, dose information was extracted from prescription/ dispensing files. Due to incomplete availability of dose information across data sources and because valproate dosing was expected to vary across episodes and regions, analyses stratified by dose were not conducted as planned.

9.4.2. Alternative medications (Objective 4)

We identified alternative treatments used by valproate-users during and after discontinuing valproate.

Alternatives for epilepsy treatment:

- Carbamazepine, phenobarbital, phenytoin, primidone, clobazam, clonazepam, eslicarbazepine acetate, lamotrigine, oxcarbazepine, perampanel, rufinamide, topiramate, zonisamide, brivaracetam, ethosuximide, gabapentin, lacosamide, levetiracetam, pregabalin, tiagabine, vigabatrin.

Alternatives for bipolar disorder treatment (maintenance):

- Lithium, quetiapine, olanzapine or lamotrigine.

Alternatives for migraine prophylaxis:

- Beta-blocker, topiramate, amitriptyline, flunarizine, pizotifen, clonidine.

Operationalisation

The occurrence of switches from valproate to alternative medications was defined as the occurrence of a prescription of an alternative medication during an episode of valproate use or within the 90-day period of discontinuation. If a prescription of an alternative medication occurred after valproate discontinuation (after 90 days of the episode end), this was not considered as a switch.

9.4.3. Outcomes

Reason for discontinuation (Objective 1)

Operationalisation

The reason for discontinuation was categorised as pregnancy wish, pregnancy, adverse drug reaction (ADR, tremor and nausea), multiple or unknown during the 3 months preceding discontinuation. Due to a lack of available free-text information in the contributing databases, reasons for discontinuation were based on coded information.

Pregnancy wish was coded as the reason for discontinuation if a female was prescribed folic acid during a treatment episode, which ends with discontinuation (according to discontinuation criteria), or 90 days after discontinuation.

Pregnancy was assumed as the reason for discontinuation if a pregnancy start was observed during a treatment episode which ends with discontinuation (according to discontinuation criteria).

ADRs were assumed if a known valproate-associated ADR event was recorded during an exposure period which ends with discontinuation (according to discontinuation criteria). ADRs with classification of "very common" (>1/10) in the SmPC for valproate were considered: nausea and tremor.

Because specific codes for drug ineffectiveness do not exist in the coding systems used by the data sources in this study and ineffectiveness cannot be assumed from repeated codes for drug indications, ineffectiveness was not assessed. Rather, all discontinuations not meeting criteria specified above for pregnancy, pregnancy wish, and ADR were classified as 'unknown'.

Subjects who met multiple of these criteria were considered separately, classified as 'multiple'.

Pregnancy testing (Objective 2)

Operationalisation

Pregnancy testing was defined as any record of a pregnancy test, prescribed or witnessed. Pregnancy testing was labelled as appropriate (Objective 5) if pregnancy testing was performed prior to *and* after prescribing/dispensing of valproate.

Timing

Pregnancy testing was defined as prior to initiation of treatment if a code for testing was recorded up to 90 days prior to a valproate record. Testing during valproate use was defined as a test code recorded within 90 days following a valproate record.

Contraceptives measures (Objective 2)

Effective contraception was defined as at least one user-independent method applied by the woman (permanent or non-permanent), or a hormone-based method combined with a barrier method. As the barrier method cannot be assessed reliably, it was not considered. Episodes of contraception were constructed using the individual schemes of dosing and effect duration described below.

Barrier, user-dependent methods:

Contraceptive diaphragm or cap, male condom, and female condom were not ascertainable from data sources.

Hormone-based user-dependent methods

Vaginal ring (28 days, including 21 days using and one week off), contraceptive patch (28 days, using for 3 weeks, one week off), progestogen only pill or desogestrel progestogen-only pill (28 days continuously), combination pills (28 days, as 21 days using and one week off). Based upon ATC/BNF codes, prescription dates, and a fixed assumed duration of 28 days for each hormone-based user-dependent method, contraception coverage episodes were constructed.

User-independent non-permanent methods

Contraceptive implant (progestogen releasing: 3 years), contraceptive injection (progestogen releasing 12 weeks), intrauterine device (coil: 3 years), intrauterine system (progestogen releasing 3 years). Based upon ATC/BNF and procedure codes, prescription dates, and units prescribed for each user-independent non-permanent method, and a fixed assumed duration for each of the methods (as described above), contraception coverage episodes were constructed.

User-independent permanent methods

Female sterilisation and hysterectomy. Because the data sources used did not allow for family linkage, male partner sterilisation (vasectomy) was not considered. Subjects were censored when a record of sterilisation or hysterectomy was observed, as they no longer were in the population of female subjects of child-bearing potential.

Pregnancy (Objective 3)

Operationalisation

To properly identify pregnancies across databases, we applied a pregnancy algorithm developed by Gini R, *et al* within the framework of the ConcePTION project (<https://www.imi-conception.eu/>). This builds directly on top of a published algorithm for detecting pregnancies by Matcho *et al*.²⁷ The strategy for defining and validating pregnancies using disparate electronic information is described in **Annex 4a**, and a list of codes used by some data sources to identify pregnancies is found in **Annex 4b**.

Briefly, the proposed pregnancy algorithm allowed the identification of past and ongoing pregnancies from 4 main streams: perinatal or birth registries, administrative data banks using diagnosis codes, and a tailored-combined stream, which uses additional data from medical observations (item-sets). The algorithm first identifies pregnancies from any possible records and subsequently establishes the start and end date of pregnancy by processing all the available information on a hierarchical manner. Hierarchy is based on the quality of records. There were four colour indicators for quality of records of pregnancies: A colour code "Green" was assigned when both pregnancy start_date and pregnancy end_date were recorded in the database; "Yellow" shows that pregnancy end_date was recorded but pregnancy start date was imputed; "Blue" indicates that pregnancy start_date was recorded in the database and pregnancy end date was imputed; and the colour code "Red" represents a pregnancy event for which both pregnancy start and end dates were imputed. Hence, green shows the highest quality and red indicates the lowest one to ascertain a pregnancy event from all data available in the database (**Annex 4a**). This framework was applied for ARS, PHARMO and BIFAP while CPRD used a different strategy.²⁸ However, PHARMO was only able to include in the algorithm the perinatal registry except in the first few years of the study period.

9.4.4. Other variables

Indication of use (Objectives 1-4)

Operationalisation

Valproate may be indicated for epilepsy, bipolar disorder or migraine prophylaxis. We used the documented ICD/ Read/ ICPC/ SNOMED-coded diagnosis (3 months between diagnosis date and valproate treatment date) in the databases as a proxy of the indication (see **Annex 5** for all code lists). In the absence of an indication in the 3-month prior window, earlier records were examined to identify the likely indication. If the likely indication could not be determined, the indication was labelled as the category “unknown”. Subjects with more than one of the indications of interest were reported separately.

Age (Objectives 1-4)

Operationalisation

Age of the subjects were calculated from date of birth and categorised as 12-20, 21-30, 31-40, 41-55 years. For study baseline measurements, a woman’s age was defined as the year of entry into the study. For objectives 1-4, age was defined as the age at which the outcome occurred (e.g., age determined by year of valproate exposure episode or year of pregnancy).

9.5. PRAC intervention

Although EMA released a statement on the recommendations and PPP in March 2018, the start and duration of implementation varied across regions and between products. The dates of the first and last actions in the implementation of the PPP across the regions included in this study, as gathered by the EMA, are presented below in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Start and end dates of the implementation of the Pregnancy Prevention Programme, per county.

<i>Country</i>	<i>Start date</i>	<i>End date</i>
Denmark	16-07-2018	11-10-2018
Italy	08-08-2018	02-10-2018
Netherlands	10-08-2018	12-12-2018
Spain	24-07-2018	01-12-2018
United Kingdom	30-04-2018	31-07-2018

9.6. Strategy for distributed analyses

This study has been conducted in a distributed manner using the ConcePTION Common Data Model (CDM) and common analytics. The CDM has been described in full elsewhere.²⁹ Federated analyses, such as in this study, have been used successfully in several other European multi-database projects.³⁰ This approach was taken to support the standardisation of analyses across data sources in the study and to improve transparency of the process of evidence generation. According to the

ConcePTION CDM and analysis pipeline, codes are linked to concepts but remain in their original format. The quality control processes explained in Sections 9.9 and 10.1 are also strongly related to this CDM procedure. **Figure 2** illustrates the data processing steps, going from original data, stored locally by the DAP to generation of analytical data sets on which the final analyses were run. All of the data sets described in Figure 2 remained local with the DAP, and data processing and analysis steps were performed by DAPs using common analytical scripts provided by the central statisticians. Only the results of the data quality checks and analyses were uploaded to a central, secure platform of Utrecht University.

Figure 2. Steps of the data processing between original data and the analytical dataset, revisited from (Gini et al, 2016).

The Extract, Transform and Load (ETL) process from original data to the ConcePTION CDM was assisted by an ETL standard template (see **Annex 6**) defining the link between source data (original data banks) to the target tables of the CDM. For each table and column to be populated in the CDM, the following information was collected: (i) the rule that feeds each target column based on source columns and/or context information, and (ii) the rule that generates target record(s) from each source record. All DAPs had interviews with trained members of the core team before filling the ETL, where they mapped_out general information about their available contents and tables; during the template filling process, to help and clarify doubts; and a last short interview to check whether there were any errors. This way, it was aimed to prevent from potential issues or adaptations needed before the script conversion execution. During the quality check process (see Section 9.4), the design of the ETL process underwent multiple rounds of revision by each DAP, until DAPs and the central statisticians were satisfied that the ETL process was of high quality. The mapping of data to a CDM then permitted common analysis scripts to be run to process the data stored locally and generate analysis results.

Study scripts were developed in an iterative manner. First, draft scripts were sent to each DAP centre to run. Following this, output was reviewed by each DAP team and the central statistician team, including counts of key study variables and population distributions. Based on the review and any errors or warnings produced by the scripts, refinements to the scripts were made. The final analysis scripts, Version 4.1, are open source and publicly available at: <https://github.com/LOT4/LOT4STUDIES>.

9.7. Data analysis

9.7.1. Analysis of Demographics and Baseline Characteristics

The source population and study population from each database were described in numbers and person-time by age, and calendar year. Valproate users were described in terms of baseline characteristics (first prescription/ dispensing in follow-up) with the following variables: age, indication, incident/ prevalent, concomitant use of alternative treatments (prescribed before and lasting until first valproate prescription/dispensing). Frequency tables were generated for categorical

variables. The proportion of missing data for each variable were reported as well as the proportion of treatment episodes estimated using population averages, per country.

9.7.2. Statistical methods

Monthly prevalence and incidence rates (of valproate use)

Prevalent (ongoing) use of valproate was estimated and defined as the number of female valproate users of childbearing age during the month of interest (at least one day of valproate exposure) divided by the total number of female subjects of childbearing age (with at least one day of follow-up) per month.

To quantify changes in number of incident valproate users over the study period (i.e., individuals who started a valproate for the first time since the study start, also considering the 1-year look-back period of 2009), monthly rates of incident users were calculated as the number of female valproate initiators of childbearing age during the month of interest divided by the total number of person-time per month.

Interrupted time series analysis

To test the effect of the 2018 RMMs on outcomes, ITS analyses were conducted. Segmented generalised least squares regression analysis was used to compare the pre-intervention (2010-2018) and post-intervention (2018-2020) level and trend changes in each of the tested outcomes. The timing of intervention was defined as described in Section 9.5. The cut-off point for intervention to run the ITS analysis was set as the first month of the implementation window from **Table 2** for each database, and the remaining months of the implementation window were excluded from the ITS model to avoid mingling of pre- and post-intervention periods. A slope and level-change impact model with two segments was used: segment 1 modelled constant pre-intervention outcome, segment 2 modelled post-intervention outcomes. Regression coefficients (interpretable as incident rate ratios), confidence intervals and p-values were estimated. For all analyses, data were used from 01 January 2010 until the last date of available information (see Section 10.1 for details).

Key assumptions of the Poisson regression models were tested. First-order autocorrelation was tested with the Durbin-Watson statistic and graphically with autocorrelation function plots.³¹ Second, overdispersion of the Poisson models was checked according to the dispersion parameter. If overdispersion was detected, negative binomial regression models were used instead of Poisson models for the segmented regression analyses. Finally, for the analysis of pregnancy testing, mixed-effects Poisson models (with random intercepts) were applied to account for clustering of pregnancy testing within-prescribers.

Pooled analyses

The beta coefficients produced from ITS analyses of each objective were presented separately per country, using forest plots.

9.7.3. Statistical analysis

Objective 1: Valproate use and discontinuation

The prevalence and incidence rate of valproate use over the study period (based on dispensing records, or when unavailable, prescription records) were estimated as described in section 9.7.2. Calculations were stratified by age categories and indication and were conducted per each DAP. In addition, monthly rates of prevalent use were stratified by categories of the duration of treatment episode (up until that month). ITS analyses were conducted to compare i) the trend in monthly

prevalent use of valproate and ii) the trend in monthly incident use of valproate before and after the period of intervention (as described in Section 9.7.2), conducted for each DAP. The ITS analysis tested the null hypotheses that there was no difference between pre- and post-intervention trends in monthly prevalent or incident use of valproates.

To assess discontinuation, the numbers of discontinuers (as defined in Section 9.4) were counted per month, and the proportion of discontinuation were calculated as the number of female subjects who discontinued valproate within a month divided by the total number of valproate users in the previous period. This was conducted for each DAP, and stratified by indication, age group, duration of treatment and reason for discontinuation (ADR, pregnancy wish, pregnancy, other). In addition, Kaplan-Meier curves for drug "survival" (the proportion of patients still being treated after a given number of days) were produced pre- and post-implementation of the PPP. To do this, the start of follow-up ("t=0") was set as the date of incident valproate prescription/ dispensing. Log rank tests were applied to test for differences between subgroups of interest (indication, age, country). ITS analyses were conducted to compare the monthly frequencies of valproate discontinuation before and after the period of intervention stratified by country and indication.

Objective 2: Prescriber compliance

Compliance of prescribers with recommendations for valproate-containing medicinal products were analysed on a prescription level (each valproate prescription) and assessed in two separate analyses: 1) pregnancy testing confirmed by healthcare professional before valproate prescription (start of an episode) and during use and 2) prescription/ implementation of contraceptive methods before and the proportion of valproate prescriptions that occurred within a period of contraception.

First, the proportions of valproate prescriptions with which a physician-confirmed pregnancy test was recorded in i) up to 90 days prior to the date of prescription/ dispensing and ii) 90 days following a prescription were calculated per month, for each DAP, and stratified by indication, age group and duration of valproate. An ITS analysis was conducted to test for a change in frequency of pregnancy testing (prior to and after prescription) before and after the 2018 intervention, with time points per month-year, for each DAP. We tested the null hypothesis that there was no difference between trends in monthly frequency of pregnancy testing in female subjects prescribed valproates pre- and post-intervention.

Second, the proportion of valproate prescriptions alongside which a contraceptive method was prescribed (within 90 days prior to the date of valproate prescription) was calculated per month, per each DAP, and stratified by indication, age group and duration of valproate. In addition, we calculated the monthly proportion of valproate prescriptions that occurred during an episode of contraception (constructed as described in section 9.4), stratified by type of contraception. An ITS analysis was conducted to test for a change in the proportion of compliant (during a period of contraception coverage) valproate prescriptions after the intervention, with time points per month-year, for each DAP. We tested the null hypothesis that there was no difference between trends in monthly compliant valproate prescriptions pre- and post-intervention.

Objective 3: Pregnancy

The occurrence of a pregnancy event during a valproate exposure have been assessed using two analytic methods. In first one (i.e., Analytic method A), we counted the monthly occurrence of a valproate prescription/ dispensing during a pregnancy time window, as medication use during pregnancy. For this, we only counted the first date of a valproate prescription/ dispensing and removed any other prescription/ dispensing dates to avoid duplicate counting of events during the same pregnancy for each unique patient. In second one (i.e., Analytic method B), we counted the monthly occurrence of start of a pregnancy during a treatment episode of valproate. For this we did not remove multiple potential pregnancies that might have occurred in the same patient during a (long) treatment with valproate, as each could represent the teratogenic risk to a unique foetus. For

both sub-objectives, we produced rates per number of prevalent users of valproates each month, and also aggregated counts and rates per each year and for the whole study period before and after the 2018 RMMs, per each database. The analyses of concurrent pregnancy events were conducted with respect to the quality colour codes of the detected pregnancies as described in section 9.4.3. When sample size was sufficient, we also aimed to run an ITS analysis to test for a change in incidence of pregnancies during valproate exposure after the intervention, per each DAP.

Objective 4: Alternative medications

Use of alternative medications in female subjects who were prevalent users or initiators of valproate during the study period, was counted per month and defined as the number of prescriptions/dispensings per month, for each country. Counts were reported separately for medications relating to each of the three indications for valproate (see **section 9.4.2**). The monthly incidence of treatment switches (as defined in section 9.4) was estimated as the number of female subjects who switched in a month divided by the total number of current valproate users that month. ITS analyses were conducted to test for a change in frequency of switches to alternative medications after the intervention, with time points per month-year, for each DAP. We tested the null hypothesis that there was no difference between trends in the monthly frequency of switches to alternative medication in female subjects prescribed valproates pre- and post-intervention.

Objective 5: Assessment of overall effectiveness

An overall assessment of the effectiveness of the 2018 RMMs was made based on the results of the analyses within Objectives 1-4. Descriptive findings were interpreted in accordance with the definition of appropriate and inappropriate use according to the CMDh (21 March 2018), as far as possible given the data available within the included databases.

The intervention was determined to be effective if a decrease is observed in the monthly incident and prevalent of inappropriate use of valproates, and this is supported by findings of statistical tests for changes in the individual components: increase in the amount of contraceptive use in valproate users, increase in the amount of pregnancy testing in valproate users and a decrease in pregnancies in valproate users. The intervention was determined to be completely successful upon evidence of a positive impact on all three outcomes or partially successful if one or two outcomes improved.

Missing data

Since the underlying data represented attended medical care, we generally assume that absence of information of clinical events means absence of that condition. No imputation was done for missing data.

Sensitivity analyses

The following sensitivity analyses were conducted in addition to the main analyses:

- Objectives 1-4: The study period was restricted to end of February 2020, to investigate the impact of excluding the time period affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, which is known to have impacted on health care seeking behaviour and collection of prescriptions. In addition, the pre-intervention time period for ITS analyses was restricted to 01 January 2015, to assess whether possible non-constant pre-intervention time trends (due to additional 2014 RMMs) might have influenced the results of the ITS analysis.
- Objectives 1,4: The discontinuation period for valproate use was reduced to 30 days when defining treatment episodes, discontinuation and switching.
- Objective 2: The window for contraceptive coverage prior to prescription was reduced to 30 days (instead of 90 days in the main analyses).

- Objective 2: The window of appropriate pregnancy testing prior to and during a valproate treatment episode was reduced to 30 days (instead of 90 days in the main analyses). This analysis was not conducted due to poor capture of pregnancy testing information.

The sensitivity analyses were conducted individually and not in combination.

9.8. Quality management

This study bears an ENCePP Seal and is registered in the EU PAS register (EUPAS31001).

The study was conducted according to the guidelines for Good Pharmacoepidemiology Practice (GPP) (International Society for Pharmacoepidemiology 2008) and according to the ENCePP code of conduct (European Medicines Agency 2018). All data access providers had experience in conducting pharmacoepidemiological research and research was done by researchers trained in pharmacoepidemiology. All programs were programmed according to agreed coding standards and were validated by double programming or source code review with second programmer involvement. Only validated software (R and/or SAS version 9.4, SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC) was used for statistical analyses.

The members of the consortium had similar local quality assurance systems in place. In addition, several quality assurance measures have been taken and maintained in the consortium across the centres, such as adherence to the ENCePP code of conduct and acquiring of the ENCePP Seal, development of protocols according the ENCePP guidance, registration of protocols at the ENCePP registry of studies, sharing and comparison of program codes across centres, documentation of harmonisation of coding systems across multiple datasets (exposure, outcome, confounder definitions), and blinded conduct of studies. Study protocols were peer-reviewed by an advisor (at least one member of the consortium that was not leading nor actively participating in the study). Regarding conflict of interest, a declaration of conflict of interest from the principal investigators or co-investigators have been presented to the Steering Committee.

The Division of Pharmacoepidemiology & Clinical Pharmacology is working according to a quality management system based on ISO 9001 principles. The quality management system is system and process oriented and based on continuous improvement. All primary and secondary processes within the division are included in the quality system, from creating research proposals, through managing PhD projects to data management, reporting and archival. The system is based upon standard operating procedures implemented throughout the division with regular internal audits as well as external audits that lead to certification. The quality management system is based on national and international external quality requirements where available and pertinent, including the guidelines for Good Pharmacoepidemiological Practices, ENCePP Guide on Methodological Standards in Pharmacoepidemiology, Good Clinical Practice, and Good Clinical Data Management Practice as well as national and international guidelines and legislation concerning data-handling and privacy issues.

Aggregated data has been stored on YODA, an Utrecht University's institutional research data repository, registered at RE3DATA.org. YODA complies with Utrecht University's information security policy for data classified as public, internal use or sensitive. All YODA data is stored in at least two geographically spread locations. The data is stored and transmitted in an encrypted format. All researchers who needed access to YODA were trained and monitored by the data management group.

9.9. Checking of data quality

The data quality and characterisation checks described below have been taken place in collaboration with our DAPs. All data remained local and only summary measures described below were inspected

in collaboration with the core team at the Utrecht University/ UMC Utrecht. This process was conducted iteratively in collaboration with each DAP until consensus regarding acceptable data quality and fitness for purpose has been reached.

Level 1 data checks reviewed the completeness and content of each variable in each table to ensure that the required variables contain data and conform to the formats specified by the CDM specifications (e.g., data types, variable lengths, formats, acceptable values, etc.). This check was conducted in collaboration with DAPs to verify that the ETL procedure to convert from source data to the CDM had been completed as expected. Formats for all values were assessed and compared to a list of acceptable formats. Missingness for core variables such as date of birth or sex were assessed at this stage. Frequency tables of variables with finite allowable values were created to identify unacceptable values. Counts of codes for events and exposures of interest in each data source were tabulated. The scripts for this level and instructions for running can be found publicly in the following link: <https://github.com/IMI-ConcePTION/Level-1-checks>.

Level 2 data checks assessed the logical relationship and integrity of data values within a variable or between two or more variables within and between tables. At this stage, we checked for internal consistency between variables, to verify for example that all health encounters had occurred on or after an individual's date of birth. The scripts for this level and instructions for running can be found publicly in the following link: <https://github.com/IMI-ConcePTION/Level-2-checks>.

Level 3 data checks examined data distributions and trends over time, by examining output by year and year/month, for each DAP's databases. For example, a level 3 data check was to ensure that there is no large, unexpected increase or decrease in records, cuts or peaks over time. In this check, we calculated person-time in female subjects of child-bearing potential by calendar year and database. We have also calculated incidence of valproate prescriptions by calendar year, database and indication, as well as incidence of various events diagnoses by calendar year and database. By comparing these types of summary measures across data sources and over time, anomalies and errors which can be corrected in partnership with data sources have become apparent. The scripts for this level and instructions for running can be found publicly in the following link: <https://github.com/IMI-ConcePTION/Level-3-checks>.

The core team has developed two separate quality check sheets, the "summarised" and the "comprehensive/ approval form" for each of the Level 1-3 data checks, to help with evaluating the output of these checks. The quality check sheet templates are attached as **Annex 7**. The forms have been developed to assess the output of Level 1-3 checks in a short, efficient and pragmatic way, from programming as well as pharmacoepidemiological and clinical perspectives. DAPs uploaded the output of the Level 1-3 checks on YODA, Utrecht University's institutional research data repository, where the core team (at UU/ UMCU) could review based on the above forms. All DAPs were also invited to review the output of their data quality checks by means of these forms, and any issues or questions regarding the quality checks were discussed in 1-1 meetings with the core team. In case of any issues with ETL of data, quality of data, or running the scripts, the core team provided programming support to the DAP. There were usually several such meetings, organised in a weekly manner, to resolve any quality issues with data for each DAP, and this process has been continued until resolving of all the issues and questions.

10. Results

This section starts with our findings in the quality control process and benchmarking, which informed us about the availability of various parameters from each data source for conducting the main, secondary and sensitivity analyses. For each ITS analysis conducted, a sensitivity analysis is present below where the study period was truncated to start at 1st January 2015 and end 29th February 2020, to investigate the impact of potential extraneous events (2015 RMMs and 2020 COVID-19 pandemic) on the analyses. Then, the main results are reported for each objective. All detailed results (including subgroup and sensitivity analysis) for each objective and for each DAP are available in **Annex 9**.

10.1. Results checking and benchmarking

In addition to the data quality checks after the ETL process with the ConcePTION CDM, the core team has also checked the output of the preliminary and main analyses from all DAPs. In order to do this, we ran an internal and an external validation of the baseline tables and counts and rates of all key study parameters. The internal validation was performed according to the known information on the individual database, size of the study population for each DAP, availability of specific study parameters in each database, and previous information collected during the Level 1-3 data checks in the previous step. The external validation benefited from a “benchmarking sheet” with some global, regional and country-level information on incidence or prevalence rates of all key study parameters, produced by the core team after a thorough review of existing data in literature.

For the purposes of results checking at this stage, the core team has developed two separate checklists, one to review the produced output of the preliminary and main analyses by each DAP, to see if there is any major or minor output missing or if there is any unexpected value produced. The second checklist aimed to evaluate the produced counts and rates from each DAP and to compare them with the benchmarking values that was already collected in the benchmarking sheet. **Annex 8** shows the combined review form, benchmarking checklist and benchmarking sheet that were used for internal and external validation of the study results. DAPs uploaded the analyses output on YODA, where the core team can access and review the output and consult any issues arose in weekly 1-1 meetings with them. The goal was to discuss any issues or errors that DAPs faced when running the scripts, or to detect and fix any bug or inaccuracy in the script of the common analytics, and to rerun the analyses at each centre level. This process was iterated until all the found issues were resolved, and there was a good sense of trust in internal and external validity of the produced output by taking into consideration the specific limitations of data and database at each centre.

The important conclusion of the two processes of “data quality checking” and “results checking and benchmarking” was to collect some detailed information on the current availability of various data from the included databases in this study. This information was crucial in determining to which analyses in different objectives each data source could contribute to. **Table 1** lists a summary of this information, which served as the basis for the main and stratified analyses in this study. As seen in **Table 1**, the data available for this study from the DNR was limited due to access delays, which prevented access to birth information, diagnostic or procedural information from the registers. The Danish data available in this study came from another study with similar purpose to study the impact of risk minimisation measures on drug utilisation, including among other on anti-epileptics and contraceptives. The sample included only users of anti-epileptics and contraceptives in the eligible Danish population. Therefore, in order to estimate rates of utilisation and other events, external population-level data was used to provide approximate numbers of the total eligible Danish population in the study, to be used as a denominator in several analyses. Also, the stratification of analyses by dose of valproates in objective 1 was not feasible due to impossibility of running

distributed analyses on dose of drugs considering heterogenous records of dosing information from various data sources.

We originally planned to conduct pooled analyses on the output of ITS analyses for various objectives and per each data source, by using a one-stage meta-analysis. However, due to substantial heterogeneity in valproate use and data capture between data sources, leading oftentimes to heterogeneity in the results from different data sources, valid pooling was not possible and was therefore not conducted. Instead, forest plots were used to depict the beta coefficients of ITS analyses from all DAPs in one place together.

Table 3. Summary of the contribution from each of data source to the analyses, based on the findings of data availability, preliminary results checking and benchmarking.

Analysis	DNR, DK	ARS Tuscany, IT	PHARMO, NL	BIFAP, ES	CPRD, UK
Objective 1: valproate utilisation and discontinuation	Included in the analysis. <i>No diagnosis codes for indication, reason for discontinuation and pregnancy strata. No data on folic acid.</i>	Included in the analysis. Limited diagnosis codes for indications and reason for discontinuation strata.	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.
Objective 2a: pregnancy tests	Excluded from the analysis. <i>Pregnancy tests not captured.</i>	Excluded from the analysis. <i>Pregnancy tests not captured.</i>	Excluded from the analysis. <i>Pregnancy tests not captured.</i>	Included in the analysis	Excluded from the analysis. <i>Limited data on pregnancy tests.</i>
Objective 2b: contraception	Included in the analysis.	Excluded from the analysis. <i>Contraception insufficiently captured to analyse.</i>	Included in the analyses.	Included in the analysis	Included in the analyses.
Objective 3: pregnancy	Excluded from the analysis. <i>No available data on pregnancies.</i>	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.
Objective 4: alternative medications	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.

Abbreviations, ITSA: interrupted time series analysis.

10.2. Description of the study population

10.2.1. For Study Objective 1

A total of 9,699,371 female subjects of childbearing age from the five participating centres were included in the study population. The largest study population was from BIFAP in Spain (N=5.1 million included female subjects). **Table 4** describes the baseline characteristics of the study population by database. The median follow-up time ranged from 3.5 years (interquartile range [IQR] 3.8) in CPRD to 10.0 years (IQR 2.4) in PHARMO. The mean age at the start of follow-up was similar across data sources, ranging from 29.8 years in PHARMO to 33.8 years in ARS Tuscany. In DNR, ARS Tuscany, BIFAP and CPRD, more people entered the study at an older age (i.e., within 41.0-55.0 years), whereas in PHARMO more people entered the study at a younger age (i.e., within 12.0-20.9 years).

Table 4. Baseline characteristics of the study population within the different databases in Denmark, Italy, Netherlands, Spain, and United Kingdom (for Objective 1).

	Denmark, DNR N=1,575,216	Italy, ARS Tuscany N=1,117,251	The Netherlands, PHARMO N=591,500	Spain, BIFAP N=5,066,393	United Kingdom, CPRD GOLD N=1,349,011
Median follow-up, years (IQR)	7.6 (3.9)	8.2 (6.8)	10.0 (2.4)	9.4 (6.4)	3.5 (3.8)
<i>Age</i>					
Mean age at index date (years, SD)	30.8 (13.0)	33.8 (13.3)	29.8 (13.3)	31.7 (13.0)	32.0 (12.6)
12.0-20.9 years (%)	306,370 (19.4%)	244,952 (21.9%)	188,176 (31.8%)	1,212,120 (23.9%)	292,123 (21.7%)
21.0-30.9 years (%)	315,625 (20.0%)	181,458 (16.2%)	121,343 (20.5%)	1,107,176 (21.9%)	346,840 (25.7%)
31.0-40.9 years (%)	372,708 (23.7%)	279,584 (25.0%)	121,455 (20.5%)	1,272,723 (25.1%)	308,936 (22.9%)
41.0-55.0 years (%)	580,513 (36.9%)	411,257 (36.8%)	160,526 (27.1%)	1,474,374 (29.%)	401,112 (29.7%)

Abbreviations, IQR: interquartile range, SD: standard deviation.

10.2.2. For Study Objective 2, 3, and 4

A total of 69,533 female subjects of childbearing age who used valproates were included in the sub-population for these objectives, where the largest subpopulation was from ARS Tuscany (N=29,093), also the highest percentage of its total population being valproate users (2.6%). **Table 5** describes the baseline characteristics of this sub-population by database. The median follow-up time ranged between 4.4 years (IQR 3.9 years) for CPRD and 11.0 years (IQR 4.4 years) for ARS Tuscany. The mean age at the start of follow-up was always >30 years, ranging between 33.9 years (for DNR) and 37.0 years (for UK CPRD). Similar across all databases, most patients were started to follow up at the highest age stratum (i.e., 41.0-55.0 years).

Table 5. Baseline characteristics of the valproate users within the different databases in Denmark, Italy, Netherlands, Spain, and United Kingdom (for Objectives 2, 3 & 4).

	Denmark, DNR N=9159 (0.5% total subjects)	Italy, ARS Tuscany N=29,093 (2.6% total subjects)	The Netherlands, PHARMO N=2725 (0.5% total subjects)	Spain, BIFAP N=22,325 (0.4% total subjects)	United Kingdom, CPRD N=6231 (0.5% total subjects)
Median follow-up, years (IQR)	8.7 (2.0)	11.0 (4.4)	10.0 (1.4)	10.0 (3.9)	4.4 (3.9)
<i>Age</i>					
Mean age at index date* (years, SD)	33.9 (12.4)	36.5 (11.3)	34.4 (12.3)	34.7 (12.1)	37.0 (11.7)
12.0-20.9 years (%)	1801 (19.7%)	3648 (12.5%)	510 (18.7%)	3630 (16.3%)	699 (11.2%)
21.0-30.9 years (%)	1749 (19.1%)	4216 (14.5%)	455 (16.7%)	3903 (17.5%)	1098 (17.6%)
31.0-40.9 years (%)	2281 (24.9%)	8612 (29.6%)	693 (25.4%)	6362 (28.5%)	1554 (24.9%)
41.0-55.0 years (%)	3328 (36.3%)	12,617 (43.4%)	1067 (39.2%)	8430 (37.8%)	2880 (46.2%)

Abbreviations, IQR: interquartile range, SD: standard deviation.

*Index date is defined as the date of entry into the study (the latest of 01 January 2010, the date the subject entered the underlying population of data source, or the subject's 12th birthday).

10.3. Main results

10.3.1. Objective 1 - Valproate utilisation and discontinuation

In the whole study period, 69,533 female subjects were prescribed or dispensed a valproate at least once across the five data sources. The monthly incidence rate of valproate use ranged between 0.02 and 0.06 per 1000 person months (PMs) in DNR, between 0.12 and 0.47 in ARS database, between 0.01 and 0.06 in PHARMO database, between 0.01 and 0.10 in BIFAP, and between 0.02 and 0.09 in CPRD. There was an observable declining trend in incidence rate of valproates across all databases over the study period. The stratified analyses of incident users by age showed that most of the new users of valproates belonged to age group 41-55 years in all databases. The stratified analyses by indication revealed that a vast majority of indications of incident use of valproates was "unknown" for ARS Tuscany (with a monthly range of 83-96%), BIFAP (47-88%) and PHARMO (69-100%), while in CPRD we observed also epilepsy, migraine and bipolar diseases in a relatively similar range as "unknown" (20-55%). The detailed results per different stratifications including the corresponding visualisation in form of line graphs are available in **Annex 9**.

The monthly prevalence rate of valproate use ranged between 1.9 and 2.2 per 1000 female subjects of childbearing age in DNR, between 6.1 and 7.7 in ARS database, between 1.2 and 1.6 in PHARMO database, between 1.3 and 2.0 in BIFAP, and between 1.9 and 3.2 in CPRD, when excluding the outliers. Stratification of prevalence counts by age showed that most of the prevalent (current) users

of valproates were in the age stratum 41-55 years, and younger age strata were following this (**figure 3**). Similar to findings of the secondary analyses of incident counts, “unknown” constituted the majority of indications for prevalent users in ARS Tuscany (unknown with a monthly range of 70-94%), BIFAP (67-94%) and PHARMO (81-97%), while in CPRD epilepsy was the leading indication since 06.2011 onwards (epilepsy with a monthly range of 25-56%). The stratification by treatment duration showed that there was an observable trend for a lower proportion of short-term valproate users (≤ 6 months) and a higher proportion of long-term users (> 1 year) towards the end study period in all databases. The detailed results per different stratifications including the corresponding visualisation in form of line graphs are available in **Annex 9**.

There was no statistically significant change in the level or trend in incidence rate of valproate use in none of the studied databases after the implementation of the 2018 EU RMMs (**figure 4.b-e**). The forest plot in **figure 6** shows the beta coefficients of the ITS analyses for level and trend of changes in incident use after the 2018 RMMs across DAPs. Due to lack of enough data points after the implementation of RMMs in Denmark, running an ITS analysis on data retrieved from DNR was not possible, and only the trend in rates of incident use over the study period is shown without an ITS modelling (**figure 4.a**).

When running the ITS analysis for prevalence rates, it was found that there was a statistically significant change in the trend in prevalence rate of valproate use after the implementation of the 2018 RMMs in all studied regions/ countries for which an ITS analysis was performed, including ARS Tuscany, PHARMO, BIFAP and CPRD, without a significant change in the level (**figure 5.b-e**). The forest plot in **figure 7** shows the beta coefficients of ITS analyses for level and trend in prevalent use changes after the 2018 RMMs for all DAPs. It was not possible to model the ITS analyses on data from DNR, because not enough data points were available after the 2018 RMMs for this database. Therefore, the trend in prevalence rates without ITS modelling is shown in **figure 5.a**.

Running the first sensitivity analysis by excluding the first five years of study period (with follow-up starting from 01.2015) resulted in similar findings for a significant declining trend in prevalent use of valproate in ARS Tuscany, PHARMO and BIFAP compared with the main analyses (**figure 5.b-d**). However, the same sensitivity analysis resulted in disappearance of statistical significance for a declining trend in prevalent use of valproates in CPRD (**figure 5.e**).

Figure 3. Trend in prevalent (current) use of valproates across the included databases during the study period, stratified by age group.

Figure 4. Change in level and trend in incidence rate of valproate use in five participating centres over the study period, modelled by interrupted time series analysis. The time of implementation of the 2018 risk minimisation measures for valproates is shown with a light grey bar, and the expected trend based on the pre-intervention period is shown with the dashed pink line thereafter. Note that the end of study period differs per data source. In case of DNR, the trend in incidence rate over time has been shown without any modelling with ITS analysis, as this was not possible due to limited time points after the 2018 RMMs.

Level change: 0.013 new users/1000 PM, $p=0.090$
Trend change: -0.001 new users/1000 PM, $p=0.062$

d. BIFAP, ES

Level change: 0.003 new users/1000 PM, $p=0.406$
Trend change: 0.000 new users/1000 PM, $p=0.686$

e. CPRD, UK

Level change: 0.001 new users/1000 PM, $p=0.833$
Trend change: -0.000 new users/1000 PM, $p=0.395$

Figure 5. Change in level and trend in prevalence rate of valproate use in five participating centres over the study period, modelled by interrupted time series analysis. The time of implementation of the 2018 risk minimisation measures for valproates is shown with a light grey bar, and the expected trend based on the pre-intervention period is shown with the dashed pink line thereafter. Note that the end of study period differs per data source. In case of DNR, the trend in prevalence rate over time have been shown without any modelling with ITS analysis, as this was not possible due to limited time points after the 2018 RMMs.

b. ARS Tuscany, IT

Level change: -0.110 current users/1000 persons, $p=0.292$

Trend change: -0.038 current users/1000 persons, $p=0.001^*$

"Sensitivity analysis for the period 01.01.2015 until 29.02.2020"

Level change: -0.075 current users/1000 persons, $p= 0.232$

Trend change: -0.018 current users/1000 persons, $p= 0.001^*$

c. PHARMO, NL

PR

Number prevalent users per 1000 persons

Level change: 0.026 current users/1000 persons, $p=0.269$

Trend change: -0.009 current users/1000 persons, $p=0.012^*$

“Sensitivity analysis for the period 01.2015 until 31.12.2019”

Number prevalent users per 1000 persons

Level change: -0.075 current users/1000 persons, $p= 0.232$

Trend change: -0.018 current users/1000 persons, $p= 0.001^*$

d. BIFAP, ES

Level change: 0.025 current users/1000 persons, $p=0.262$
Trend change: -0.012 current users/1000 persons, $p=0.002^*$

“Sensitivity analysis for the period 01.01.2015 until 29.02.2020”

Level change: 0.007 current users/1000 persons, $p= 0.550$
Trend change: -0.010 current users/1000 persons, $p= 0.000^*$

e. CPRD, UK

Level change: -0.009 current users/1000 persons, $p=0.803$
Trend change: -0.009 current users/1000 persons, $p=0.015^*$

“Sensitivity analysis for the period 01.01.2015 until 29.02.2020”

Level change: 0.012 current users/1000 persons, $p= 0.709$
Trend change: 0.004 current users/1000 persons, $p= 0.183$

Abbreviations, IR: incident use rate, PR: prevalent use rate.

* ITSA not conducted due to limited post-intervention data available.

Figure 6. Forest plot showing the beta coefficients of the interrupted time series analyses for change in level and trend in incidence rate of valproate use after the implementation of the 2018 risk minimisation measures for valproates across DAPs.

Abbreviations, DAP: Data Access Partner, ITS: interrupted time series.

Figure 7. Forest plot showing the beta coefficients of the interrupted time series analyses for change in level and trend in prevalence rate of valproate use after the implementation of the 2018 risk minimisation measures for valproates across DAPs.

Abbreviations, DAP: Data Access Partner, ITS: interrupted time series.

The monthly proportion of discontinuers ranged between 1.3-2.6% in DNR, 4.4-7.5% in ARS, 1.5-5.3% in PHARMO, 3.2-5.2% in BIFAP and 0.8-3.2% in CPRD, when excluding the outliers. The stratified analyses by age showed that the highest proportion of valproate discontinuers were in the age group 41-55 years across all databases. Moreover, the stratification by indication revealed that a vast majority of discontinuers had an “unknown” diagnosis registered in ARS Tuscany (with a monthly range of 77-98%), PHARMO (67-100%), BIFAP (62-92%), while in CPRD epilepsy was an important indication (13-56% monthly range for epilepsy). Regarding the reason for discontinuation, again “unknown” was the leading reason across all databases, including ARS Tuscany (with a monthly range of 97-100%), PHARMO (86-100%), BIFAP (95-100%), and CPRD (73-100%). The detailed results per different stratifications including the corresponding visualisation in form of line graphs are available in **Annex 9**.

Results of the ITS analyses showed that there was no statistically significant change in trend or level of valproate discontinuers in ARS Tuscany, PHARMO, BIFAP, and CPRD after the 2018 EU RMMs (**figure 8.b-e**). The forest plot in **figure 9** shows the beta coefficients of ITS analyses for level and trend in changes of valproate discontinuation after the 2018 RMMs for all DAPs. Due to lack of enough data points after the implementation of RMMs in Denmark, it was not possible to model the trend of discontinuers with an ITS analysis and only the trend in proportion of valproate discontinuers is shown in **figure 8.a**.

The first sensitivity analysis that excludes the time period before 01.2015 yielded similar non-significant estimates for a change in proportion of valproate discontinuers after the 2018 RMMs in ARS Tuscany, PHARMO and CPRD as in the main analyses (**figure 8.b, c & e**). But exclusion of the first five years from the ITS analyses resulted in a significant increase in level of discontinuers' proportion in BIFAP (**figure 8.d**).

Figure 8. Change in level and trend in proportion of valproate discontinuers in five participating centres over the study period. The time of implementation of the 2018 risk minimisation measures for valproates is shown with a light grey bar, and the expected trend based on the pre-intervention period is shown with the dashed pink line thereafter. Note that the end of study period differs per data source.

b. ARS Tuscany, IT

Level change: 0.227 discontinuers/100 valproate user, $p=0.235$

Trend change: -0.022 discontinuers/100 valproate user, $p=0.057$

“Sensitivity analysis for the period 01.01.2015 until 29.02.2020”

Level change: 0.365 discontinuers/100 valproate user, $p= 0.182$

Trend change: 0.005 discontinuers/100 valproate user, $p=0.812$

c. PHARMO, NL

Level change: 0.391 discontinuers/100 valproate user, $p=0.290$

Trend change: -0.034 discontinuers/100 valproate user, $p=0.483$

“Sensitivity analysis for the period 01.01.2015 until 31.12.2019”

Level change: 0.547 discontinuers/100 valproate user, $p= 0.209$

Trend change: -0.027 discontinuers/100 valproate user, $p= 0.612$

d. BIFAP, ES

Level change: 0.473 discontinuers/100 valproate user, $p=0.118$

Trend change: -0.015 discontinuers/100 valproate user, $p=0.458$

“Sensitivity analysis for the period 01.01.2015 until 29.02.2020”

Level change: 0.666 discontinuers/100 valproate user, $p= 0.000^*$

Trend change: -0.025 discontinuers/100 valproate user, $p= 0.055$

e. CPRD, UK

Level change: -0.117 discontinuers/100 valproate user, $p=0.601$

Trend change: -0.013 discontinuers/100 valproate user, $p=0.246$

“Sensitivity analysis for the period 01.01.2015 until 29.02.2020”

Level change: -0.180 discontinuers/100 valproate user, $p= 0.449$

Trend change: 0.026 discontinuers/100 valproate user, $p= 0.091$

* ITSA not conducted due to limited post-intervention data available.

Figure 9. Forest plot showing the beta coefficients of the interrupted time series analyses for change in level and trend in discontinuation rates of valproate use after the implementation of the 2018 risk minimisation measures for valproates across DAPs.

Abbreviations, DAP: Data Access Partner, ITS: interrupted time series.

10.3.2. Objective 2 – Pregnancy testing and contraception

As mentioned earlier (see **Table 1**), the information on pregnancy testing was not available from most of our included databases (with some limited information available only in BIFAP). From the total number of valproate prescriptions or dispensings in the five databases during the study period (N=71,222), only very few were accompanied by a record of a pregnancy test in the 90 days before or 90 days after the date of a prescription or dispensing, where monthly counts were always below 5. Due to this limitation, modelling of any trend change in proportion of valproate prescriptions or dispensings with an adherent pregnancy test before or after was not possible.

Similarly, we could retrieve limited information on contraceptive use during the study period from the included databases (see **Table 1**). For example, we could not evaluate the proportion of valproate prescriptions or dispensings alongside (within 90 days) or during a period of contraceptive use in ARS Tuscany, and hence no modelling for any change in trend in this proportion with an ITS analyses was performed. There was a monthly range of 11-17% (within the DNR), 8-22% (PHARMO), 0.2-6.0% (BIFAP), and 11-23% (CPRD) of valproate dispensings or prescriptions, along which there was a contraceptive prescription in the 90-days prior (**Annex 9**). Furthermore, only between 6-9% of monthly valproate dispensings in DNR, 12-23% in PHARMO, 0.3-4.4% in BIFAP, and 10-25% of valproate prescriptions in CPRD have occurred during an episode of contraceptive use, when excluding the outliers.

The stratified analysis by age revealed a similar pattern of contraceptive use with valproate prescriptions/dispensings across all age strata in the studied databases. The stratification by indication showed that “unknown” was the leading stratum across all databases (**Annex 9**). Furthermore, stratification of contraceptive use by contraceptive method showed that a fixed combination of hormonal contraceptives was the leading method in ARS Tuscany (before 2016) and BIFAP, while IUD and contraceptive injection were the leading method in PHARMO and CPRD.

The results of ITS analyses showed that the only statistically significant increase was in level of the proportion of compliant valproate dispensings in PHARMO that started during a contraceptive episode after the implementation of 2018 RMMs, although there was no change in trend (**figure 10.b**). There was no significant increase in trend or level of compliant valproate prescriptions/ dispensings with a contraceptive coverage in other databases (**figure 10.c-e**). In opposite, we noticed a declining trend in compliant valproate prescriptions with an ongoing contraceptive use in the main analysis in CPRD, which disappeared in the sensitivity analysis that only considered the period after 01.2015 (not considering the time period before the 2014 RMMs) (**figure 10.e**). Conducting an ITS modelling was not possible for DNR, as we did not have data points on any drug or contraceptive use from this database after December 2018, thus just the trend in proportion of compliant dispensings with a contraceptive coverage during the study period is shown (**figure 10.a**).

Figure 10. Change in trend in proportion of compliant valproate prescriptions/ dispensings with a contraceptive coverage in participating centres over the study period, modelled by interrupted time series analysis. The time of implementation of the 2018 risk minimisation measures for valproates is shown with a light grey bar, and the expected trend based on the pre-intervention period is shown with the dashed pink line thereafter. Note that the end of study period differs per data source. There is no output produced for ARS Tuscany, as there was limited information on contraceptive use from this database. For DNR, the trend over time have been shown without any modelling with ITS analysis, as this was not possible due to limited time points after the 2018 RMMs.

Valproate prescription/
dispensing/
starting
during a
contraceptive
episode

b. PHARMO, NL

Valproate prescription/dispensing with contraceptive use in 90 days prior

Percent prescriptions with prior contraceptive

Date

Level change: 1.961 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p=0.182$
Trend change: -0.274 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p=0.085$

"Sensitivity analysis for the period 01.01.2015 until 31.12.2019"

Percent prescriptions with prior contraceptive

Date

Level change: 2.622 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p= 0.062$
Trend change: -0.196 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p= 0.179$

Valproate prescription/dispensing starting during a contraceptive episode

Level change: 2.750 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p=0.016^*$
Trend change: -0.131 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p=0.318$

“Sensitivity analysis for the period 01.01.2015 until 31.12.2019”

Level change: 2.966 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p= 0.015^*$
Trend change: -0.169 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p= 0.192$

c. BIFAP, ES

Valproate prescription/dispensing with contraceptive use in 90 days prior

Percent prescriptions with prior contraceptive

Date

Level change: 0.453 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p=0.171$
Trend change: -0.022 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p=0.400$

“Sensitivity analysis for the period 01.01.2015 until 29.02.2020”

Percent prescriptions with prior contraceptive

Date

Level change: 0.451 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p=0.057$
Trend change: -0.012 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p=0.488$

Valproate prescription/dispensing starting during a contraceptive episode

Level change: 0.231 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p=0.402$
Trend change: -0.029 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p=0.157$

"Sensitivity analysis for the period 01.01.2015 until 29.02.2020"

Level change: 0.296 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p= 0.113$
Trend change: 0.009 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p= 0.514$

d. CPRD, UK

Valproate prescription/dispensing with contraceptive use in 90 days prior

Percent prescriptions with prior contraceptive

Level change: -2.135 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p=0.147$
Trend change: 0.076 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p=0.361$

"Sensitivity analysis for the period 01.01.2015 until 29.02.2020"

Percent prescriptions with prior contraceptive

Level change: -1.200 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p= 0.468$
Trend change: 0.074 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p= 0.587$

Valproate prescription/dispensing starting during a contraceptive episode

Percent prescriptions with ongoing contraception

Level change: -0.653 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p=0.601$
Trend change: -0.289 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p=0.020^*$

"Sensitivity analysis for the period 01.01.2015 until 29.02.2020"

Percent prescriptions with ongoing contraception

Level change: -0.013 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p= 0.988$
Trend change: 0.050 contraceptive coverage/100 valproate users, $p= 0.432$

* ITSA not conducted due to limited post-intervention data available.

10.3.3. Objective 3 – Pregnancy

In general, we observed a substantial number of concurrent new valproate prescriptions/ dispensings during a pregnancy time window, or pregnancy events during a valproate treatment episode in ARS Tuscany, BIFAP and CPRD, while there were fewer concurrent events in PHARMO (Table 6). In ARS Tuscany, we found 386 first dates of a valproate dispensings that occurred during a pregnancy time window (with the quality colour codes green and yellow) before implementation of the 2018 RMMs (i.e., from 01.2010 until 08.2018), with a rate of 0.70 per 1000 valproate users. The count and rate of such concurrent events in ARS declined to 40 and 0.27, respectively, after the 2018 RMMs. In PHARMO, we observed only 27 first dates of a concurrent valproate prescription/ dispensing with a pregnancy event (all with a colour code green) in the whole study period before 2018 RMMs, while there was no single event found in the time period afterwards. In BIFAP, there were 330 prescriptions/ dispensings of valproate in unique sets of patient-pregnancy episode (all with a quality colour code yellow) with a rate of 0.48 per 1000 drug users before the 2018 RMMs. The number of concurrent drug use/ pregnancy events reduced to 20 events with a rate of 0.13 in the time period afterwards. In contrast to other databases, we observed an increasing rate of simultaneous valproate prescriptions during pregnancy in CPRD, where 204 such events happened before 2018 RMMs (with a rate of 1.13) and 56 events post 2018 intervention (with a rate of 5.07).

The findings on counts and rates for the other sub-objective, i.e., analytic method B: start of a pregnancy during a treatment episode of valproates, were similar to the first sub-objective (i.e., analytic method A: valproate use during a pregnancy time window) (Table 6). Again, we observed the largest numbers of a concurrent pregnancy event during a valproate treatment episode in ARS Tuscany (374 before 2018 RMMs and 50 after 2018 RMMs) and BIFAP (316 before 2018 RMMs and 21 after it), and no single event in PHARMO after the 2018 RMMs. The rates in all databases were declining after the 2018 RMMs, besides CPRD where we noticed a higher rate after the 2018 intervention (1.10 per 1000 valproate user before 08.2018 vs. 6.16 afterwards).

The monthly and yearly counts of concurrent pregnancy events during valproate use for both sub-objectives in addition to data on the counts of concurrent pregnancy events with a quality colour code red (lowest validity in ascertainment) are provided in **Annex 9**.

The time distance between start of a pregnancy and prescription/ dispensing date of a valproate during a pregnancy episode has been calculated in some DAPs. In ARS Tuscany, the median distance between a pregnancy start of prescription/ dispensing date of valproates was 27 days (IQR: 48 days) with a maximum value of 278 days. In PHARMO, there was a median length of 38 days (IQR 62.5 days) and a maximum length of 272 days from start of a pregnancy until a first prescription/ dispensing of valproate during that pregnancy. In CPRD, the median length between start of a pregnancy and first prescription of a valproate was 19 days (IQR 23 days) with a maximum length of 277 days.

On the other hand, the median time distance between start of valproate treatment episode and occurrence of a pregnancy event in ARS Tuscany was 119 days (with IQR 431 days and max 4199 days), while this was 299 days (IQR 715 days) with a maximum length of 2393 days in PHARMO. Also in CPRD, there was a median of 608 days (IQR 1215 days) and a maximum of 4073 days' time distance between start of a treatment episode of valproate and occurrence of a pregnancy.

There was no data on pregnancy counts available from DNR.

Table 6. Aggregated concurrent pregnancy events during valproate exposure, stratified by the analytic method (A: valproate use during a pregnancy time window, and B: pregnancy occurrence during a valproate treatment episode) and by time period of pre- and post 2018 risk minimisation measures, across databases. Noteworthy, only those pregnancy events with a quality colour code green and yellow (highest validity in ascertainment) have been considered in this table. Also, the observed concurrent events in the two analytical methods (A and B) are overlapping.

		ARS Tuscany, IT			PHARMO, NL			BIFAP, ES			CPRD, UK		
		Concurrent pregnancies	Prevalent users of valproate s†	Rate per 1000 user	Concurrent pregnancies	Prevalent users of valproate s†	Rate per 1000 user	Concurrent pregnancies	Prevalent users of valproate s†	Rate per 1000 user	Concurrent pregnancies	Prevalent users of valproate s†	Rate per 1000 user
A. Valproate use during a pregnancy time window	Pre 2018 RMMs*	386	552,506	0.70	27	79,197	0.34	330	694,549	0.48	204	181,054	1.13
	Post 2018 RMMs*	40	150,769	0.27	0	10,896	0	20	157,981	0.13	56	11,043	5.07
B. Start of Pregnancy during a treatment episode of valproate	Pre 2018 RMMs*	374	552,506	0.68	24	79,197	0.30	316	694,549	0.45	200	181,054	1.10
	Post 2018 RMMs*	50	150,769	0.33	0	10,896	0	21	157,981	0.13	68	11,043	6.16

Abbreviations, RMM: risk minimisation measures.

* The cut-off point for a demarcation between pre- and post-intervention time periods was selected as Aug. 2018 for all DAPs, based on the implementation period of RMMs across countries.

† The number of prevalent users of valproates, used as the denominator for the rates here, is actually the sum of monthly prevalence counts for the time period pre 2018 RMMs (i.e., Jan. 2010 - Jul. 2018) and post 2018 RMMs (i.e., Aug. 2018 – end of study period for each database) in each database, which represent the sum of unique patients who were exposed each month to valproate.

10.3.4. Objective 4 – Alternative medications

Descriptive counts and rates of alternative medicine use per various indications of valproates (as listed in **Section 9.4.2**) are given in **Annex 9**. In DNR, there was an increasing trend in rates of alternative medicine use for epilepsy (ranged between 11.3 and 18.8 per 1000 PMs), and bipolar diseases (ranged between 8.1 and 13.8), and a levelling trend for migraine (ranged between 7.4 and 10.8) during the study period (**figure 11.a**). In ARS Tuscany, we noticed a gradually increasing trend in rate of alternative medication use for epilepsy during the study period (ranged between 11.2 and 16.0 per 1000 PMs) and a more pronounced increasing trend in bipolar diseases (ranged between 4.1 and 7.8), whereas the trend in use of migraine drugs remained rather steady (ranged between 7.1 and 10.0) (**figure 11.b**). In PHARMO, there was an increasing trend in rates of alternative drug use for epilepsy until 2016 and then a slightly decreasing trend towards end of the study period (ranged between 3.3 and 7.5 per 1000 PMs), whereas the trends for bipolar diseases was generally increasing (ranged between 4.0 and 8.6), and the one for migraine was mostly steady (ranged between 8.8 and 14.3), (**figure 11.c**). In BIFAP, there was a steady trend in alternative medication use for all indications during the study period (ranged between 11.3 and 15.5 per 1000 PMs for epilepsy, between 3.2 and 4.5 for bipolar diseases, and between 7.4 and 11.1 for migraine) (**figure 11.d**). In CPRD, the trend in use of all alternative medications for different indications of valproates were increasing towards the end of the study period (ranged between 14.7 and 39.0 per 1000 PMs for epilepsy, between 8.2 and 17.4 for bipolar diseases, and between 23.8 and 43.5 for migraine, between 01.2010 and 10.2020) (**figure 11.e**).

Figure 11. Monthly rates of prescribing/ dispensing of alternative medications to valproates in the overall study population per each database. Note that the end of study period differs per data source.

<p>Bipolar dis.</p>	<p>Rate of prescribing alternative bipolar medicines</p> <p>Date</p>
<p>Migraine</p>	<p>Rate of prescribing alternative migraine medicines</p> <p>Date</p>

b. ARS Tuscany, IT

Epilepsy	<p>Rate of prescribing alternative epilepsy medicines</p> <p>Date</p>
Bipolar dis.	<p>Rate of prescribing alternative bipolar medicines</p> <p>Date</p>
Migraine	<p>Rate of prescribing alternative migraine medicines</p> <p>Date</p>

c. PHARMO, NL

d. BIFAP, ES

Epilepsy	<p>Rate of prescribing alternative epilepsy medicines</p> <p>Date</p>
Bipolar dis.	<p>Rate of prescribing alternative bipolar medicines</p> <p>Date</p>
Migraine	<p>Rate of prescribing alternative migraine medicines</p> <p>Date</p>

e. CPRD, UK

<p>Epilepsy</p>	<p>Rate of prescribing alternative epilepsy medicines</p> <p>Date</p>
<p>Bipolar dis.</p>	<p>Rate of prescribing alternative bipolar medicines</p> <p>Date</p>
<p>Migraine</p>	<p>Rate of prescribing alternative migraine medicines</p> <p>Date</p>

There were different monthly rates of switching from valproates to alternative medicine across databases during the study period. In DNR, the monthly switch rate from valproates to alternative medicine ranged between 2.3 and 7.5% during the study period with a slightly decreasing trend towards the end of study period, without considering the outliers (**figure 12.a**). In ARS Tuscany, between 1.9 and 4.5% of valproate users switched to alternative medications each month with a levelling trend in switching rate as per visual inspection (**figure 12.b**). In PHARMO, there was a steady trend in switching rate within a range of 0.7-3.0% across the study period, after excluding the outliers (**figure 12.c**). In BIFAP, the monthly switching rate varied between 1.0 and 6.3% with a decreasing trend throughout, when excluding the outliers (**figure 12.d**). In CPRD, the trend in switching was slightly declining with rates ranged between 0.7 and 3.5% (**figure 12.e**).

The stratification by age of switchers from valproates to alternative medicine showed a similar pattern across the age strata, with the oldest age group (those 41-55 years) comprising the largest numbers in all databases. Moreover, "unknown" was the main indication group among switchers with a vast majority across all databases (**Annex 9**)

The ITS analysis of switching rates from valproates to alternative medicine before versus after the 2018 RMMs revealed that there was a statistically significant decrease in level and increase in trend of switchers in ARS Tuscany (**figure 12.b**). However, there was no significant change in level or trend of switchers in BIFAP (**figure 12.d**). For the other databases, such as in PHARMO and CPRD, it was not possible to model the ITS analysis because after 2018 the counts of switchers were too small (often <5) to fit a stable model, or in case of DNR there were not enough time points after the 2018 RMMs.

Figure 12. Change in trend in rate of switchers from valproates to alternative medications from the participating centres over the study period, modelled by interrupted time series analysis. The time of implementation of the 2018 risk minimisation measures for valproates is shown with a light grey bar, and the expected trend based on the pre-intervention period is shown with the dashed pink line thereafter. Note that the end of study period differs per data source. ITSA was not possible in the PHARMO and CPRD data sources because after 2018 the counts of switchers were too small (often <5) to fit a stable model. For the DNR, there were too few data points after the 2018 RMMs to conduct an ITSA. For these data sources, the trend over time has been shown instead.

b. ARS Tuscany, IT

Level change: -0.583 switchers to alternative medications/100 valproate users, $p=0.001^*$

Trend change: 0.036 switchers to alternative medications/100 valproate users, $p=0.000^*$

“Sensitivity analysis for the period 01.01.2015 until 29.02.2020”

Level change: -0.260 switchers to alternative medications/100 valproate users, $p= 0.130$

Trend change: 0.016 switchers to alternative medications/100 valproate users, $p= 0.221$

c. PHARMO, NL

Percent valproate users switched to alternative

d. BIFAP, ES

Percent valproate users switched to alternative

Level change: -0.071 switchers to alternative medications/100 valproate users, $p=0.777$
Trend change: -0.011 switchers to alternative medications/100 valproate users, $p=0.536$

“Sensitivity analysis for the period 01.01.2015 until 29.02.2020”

Percent valproate users switched to alternative

Level change: -0.098 switchers to alternative medications/100 valproate users, $p= 0.603$
Trend change: -0.287 switchers to alternative medications/100 valproate users, $p= 0.098$

e. CPRD, UK

10.4. Sensitivity analyses

The results of some a priori sensitivity analyses (i.e., running the ITS analyses on various trends in valproate utilisation or discontinuation by exclusion the first five years of study period before 01.2015) are already reported after the main results in **Section 10.3**. Full results of monthly counts and percentage of discontinuation per month, per data source, with a 30-day window of discontinuation and full results of monthly counts and percentage of prior contraception per month, per data source, with a 30-day window for prior contraception can be found in **Annex 9**.

11. Discussion

11.1. Key results

In this section, we summarise the main results of our study objectives. Then we put all the findings into a broader context, so we can also answer the objective 5, i.e., the effectiveness of the 2018 RMMs for valproates among females of childbearing age.

11.1.1. Objective 1 - Valproate utilisation and discontinuation

The aim of this analysis was to assess the utilisation and prescription patterns of valproates across the included databases from Denmark, Italy, Netherlands, Spain and United Kingdom, and to have a comparison before versus after the 2018 RMMs. We observed a statistically significant declining trend in prevalence rate of valproate use in all countries/regions, for which an ITS analysis could be performed, but no significant decreasing trend or level in incidence rate of valproate use in the studied countries/regions after the 2018 RMMs compared to the period before. The general trend in use of valproates was also declining across the study period in all databases, including DNR, for which an ITS analyses was not possible. The exclusion of the first five years of follow-up in a sensitivity analysis (to remove the period before the 2014 RMMs) resulted in disappearance of some few significant findings, but the declining trend in prevalent use of valproates after the 2018 RMMs persisted in ARS Tuscany, PHARMO, and BIFAP. Regarding the valproate discontinuers, the monthly rates ranged between 1-8% across all databases, and in none of the data sources we observed a significant increase in trend or level of valproate discontinuation after the 2018 intervention compared to the time before. The significant decrease in prevalent (current) use of valproates across databases before versus after 2018 RMMs without any decrease in incident (new) use nor any significant increase in discontinuation rates might be due to a general declining trend in (absolute number of) valproate utilisation from 2010 to 2020 across all centres. It might be also due to a changing trend in treatment duration (lower proportion of short-term [≤ 6 months] and a higher proportion of long-term valproate users [> 1 year]) towards the end of study period observed in all centres.

11.1.2. Objective 2 - Pregnancy testing and contraception

The aim of this analysis was to assess prescribers' compliance with recommendations in the SmPC for valproates, and this was quantified in form of prescribing pregnancy tests or contraceptives before starting of a treatment episode with valproates. Due to the limited data on pregnancy tests from all DAPs, modelling of any trend change in proportion of valproate prescriptions or dispensings with an adherent pregnancy test before versus after 2018 RMMs was not possible. But the rate of contraceptive coverage at the start of valproate treatment was low across all DAPs, as only 0.5-23% of valproate prescriptions/dispensings each month were accompanied by a contraceptive prescription in 90-days before, and only between 0.5-25% of new valproate treatment episode had started during contraceptive use. There was no increasing trend in compliant valproate prescriptions/dispensings with a contraceptive coverage after the 2018 RMMs across the studied databases, and the only increase in level was observed in PHARMO.

11.1.3. Objective 3 - Pregnancy

The aim of this analysis was to assess patients' effective use of contraceptives in compliance with recommendations in the SmPC for valproates, and this was quantified with the overall outcome of pregnancy events. In general, we observed a significant number of concurrent new valproate

prescriptions/dispensings during a pregnancy time window in ARS Tuscany (386 pre- and 40 post 2018 intervention), BIFAP (330 pre and 20 post) and CPRD (204 pre and 56 post), while there were fewer concurrent events in PHARMO (27 pre and 0 post). However, it must be noted that in most of the study period PHARMO only identified pregnancies from a perinatal registry, thus selecting pregnancies that ended at a later stage. This may have underestimated the occurrence of pregnancies among exposed individuals in PHARMO, while higher occurrence of valproate exposure during pregnancy in ARS, BIFAP, and CPRD could mean that they captured pregnancies ending prematurely. The results of the other sub-objective (i.e., start of a pregnancy event during a valproate treatment episode) were similar and mostly overlapping with the latter findings across databases. The rate of concurrent pregnancy events with valproate use declined in the period after the 2018 RMMs compared with the period before in most databases (ARS, BIFAP and PHARMO), but not in CPRD. This may suggest that often assessing that a pregnancy has started in a woman exposed to valproate, or assessing that a pregnant woman has been exposed to valproate, results in termination of the pregnancy. The observable higher rate of concurrent pregnancies with valproate use in CPRD before versus after the 2018 RMMs may be due to the known attrition of the CPRD GOLD databases in recent years and artificial inflation of rates with smaller denominators towards the end of study period. Due to small number of monthly events, any modelling with ITS analyses to see the changing trend after the 2018 intervention was not possible.

11.1.4. Objective 4 - Alternative medications

This objective was to investigate the drug utilisation and prescription patterns of alternative medications among women of childbearing potential and pregnant women where valproates had been previously prescribed or discontinued. We found an increasing trend in rates of alternative medicine use for epilepsy and bipolar diseases indications of valproates across the study period in most databases (i.e., DNR, ARS Tuscany, PHARMO and CPRD), while the rates for migraine were mostly steady. The monthly rate of switch from a valproate to an alternative medication was similar across all DAPs and ranged between 1-8%. The trend in switching rates was mostly declining in all databases across the study period. Running an ITS analysis was not possible for most of the included databases, but there was a significant increase in trend in switching rates from valproates to alternative medicine after the 2018 RMMs in ARS Tuscany.

11.1.5. Objective 5 - Effectiveness of the 2018 RMMs

Based on the above findings on various objectives in this study, we can conclude that in general there was a small impact of the 2018 RMMs on valproate use among women of childbearing age in our included databases. This conclusion has been driven by the generally declining trend in valproate use after the 2018 RMMs in almost all databases (Objective 1), but also no increasing trend in compliant valproate prescriptions/ dispensings with a contraceptive coverage (Objective 2), a significant increase in switching rates from valproates to alternative medications only in few regions (such as ARS Tuscany) (Objective 4), and the declining rates of concurrent pregnancy events with valproate exposure after the 2018 intervention in most countries/regions (Objective 3). Noteworthy, this conclusion should be interpreted in the context of the limitations that we faced when conducting this study. Investigating some parts of the objectives was not feasible due to limited data availability on pregnancy test or over-the-counter use of some contraceptives for example from our included databases. The occurrence of COVID-19 pandemic has also shortened and impacted our post-intervention period and limited our ability to run ITS analyses for some sub-objectives and some DAPs. However, the substantial number of concurrent pregnancy events with valproate use across most countries/regions warrants a careful monitoring of the existing policies and regulations on valproate use in Europe, to see if there is any need for additional measures in the future.

11.2. Interpretation in context of literature

There is another study conducted by the same research network (the EU PE&PV Research Network) on the risk awareness and adherence to PPP and the 2018 RMMs among patients, prescribers and pharmacists.³² This study included eight European centres (in Belgium, Denmark, Greece, Latvia, Portugal, the Netherlands, Slovenia and Spain) and was also funded by the EMA. This study found that there was high awareness of the teratogenic risks associated with valproate use during pregnancy among patients (71%), prescribers (94%), and pharmacists (95%).³² However, the use of educational materials and information tools (such as patient card, risk acknowledgement forms, and healthcare professional guides) was low, and according to respondents, the most beneficial tool was the warning symbol on packaging of drugs. These results can complement what we found in this current quantitative study with declining trend in utilisation of valproates after the 2018 RMMs, but still low rates of coverage by contraceptive methods. Considering the significant number of concurrent pregnancy events during valproate exposure in most studied databases, more attention should be paid to potentially improve the regulatory and educational measures to avoid inappropriate use of valproates in pregnant women, and to hopefully eradicate any teratogenic effect from using valproates in the next generations.

It is of note that valproate RMMs have been in place for many years. The referral in 2014 further strengthened the restrictions in use of valproate in women of childbearing potential, and this has become even more restricted in 2018.[10] A clear cut-off in 2018 to detecting an effect might not be visible on all outcomes studied, as for example the advice to use contraceptive measures was already in place before 2018, and the use of valproate in women of childbearing potential was declining since 2010. In line with the latter finding, we also observed a declining trend in valproate utilisation in this study during our study period (2010-2020). The influence from previous RMMs may have prevented us to detect a significant change for some of the outcomes studied.

11.3. Clinical and policy impact

The results of this study can hopefully inform clinicians in different specialties of the current situation of valproate use in women of childbearing age, and to give them some guidance for responsible and careful prescribing of these teratogenic drugs in such a vulnerable group. Moreover, the recent trends in the utilisation of valproates and the few concurrent occurrences of pregnancy events and valproate use - observed in several countries, should indeed inform policy makers and regulatory agencies on the current status of the situation and trigger ideas to improve it.

11.4. Strengths and limitations

11.4.1. Strengths related to the data source

In conducting this study, we had some strengths, partly owing to the choice of our data sources, and partly owing to the methodologies that we chose.

We used large nationwide EHDs from five participating European countries, which were representative of the source population of their member states, or the specific region in the member state. First, by including all female subjects of childbearing age registered in each database at any time during the study period in addition to setting minimal exclusion criteria we mitigated an effect from selection bias. Furthermore, we included all valproate containing medicinal products from every indication of use in Europe to make sure we have a full picture of the valproate utilisation in this study. Moreover, using several databases from different countries across the continent has led to a large and diverse study population with good representativeness, and generalisable results to a European and global setting.

The total sample size of around 10 million female subjects of child-bearing potential permitted the calculation of precise estimates of valproate utilisation and other outcomes on a monthly basis. In addition, analysis across five countries, where the 2018 RMMs were implemented in potentially different ways (and at different moments in 2018), allowed differences in the impact of the RMMs across different counties to be examined.

Our choice of databases had each brought its own merits and advantages. DNR gave us the opportunity to study almost all females of childbearing age in the whole country of Denmark during the study period. The Dutch PHARMO Database Network is a unique database in the Netherlands, where one can receive the complete patient history from various linked data sources. The UK CPRD is one of the largest primary care databases in the world, where numerous prior research studies conducted using this database proved its validity and richness. BIFAP gave us the opportunity to collect various information from the Spanish National Health System with data on primary care, and drugs dispensings from various regions in Spain with a large population sample size (circa 14 million patients). The ARS Tuscany databases is a regional database in Italy with valuable information on hospitalisations, drug claims, pathology reports and mortality.

11.4.2. Strengths related to methodology

A key strength of this study is the rigorous quality checking processes that were conducted. At each stage of data processing – transformation and loading to the CDM and creation of the eligible study population – rounds of review enabled any uncertainties in the data or errors in the ETL or analyses to be identified. Detailed level 1-3 checks, similar to those used by the FDA Sentinel system, ensured homogeneity and consistency in the ETL process. Any differences in the way that data were ETL'd to the CDM were seen by the investigators by comparing the outputs of the level 3 checks across data sources.

Use of the ConcePTION CDM and common analysis tools was key to minimising unwanted heterogeneity in the results due to differences in the implementation of the study. By converting all of the data sources to a standard format, it was possible to run common analysis scripts, which removed the risk of differences in the implementation of data processing steps and the analyses. By using a CDM that enforced on syntactic but not semantic harmonisation, it was possible to implement data source-specific algorithms for the definition of the duration of individual prescriptions. This allowed each DAP to use an approach that, based on their expertise with the data source, was most suitable for the research question, with the information available in the data source.

To evaluate the implementation and the effect of the EU communication on PPP with valproates, we benefited from a quasi-experimental design, i.e., the ITS analysis. This is an innovative and one of the strongest methods for drug utilisation research with an intervention when conducting an RCT is not feasible.^{33,34,35} Although the ITS design is considered the best available method to evaluate the impact of policy changes where a control group is not available, causality cannot be established, and causal inference is subject to key assumptions.

One strength of our ITS design was the ability to extract and use a large number of data points and observations, especially before the intervention.³³ This helped us to reduce any effect from fluctuations, variability and outliers in medication use across the study period.

11.4.3. Limitations related to the data source

In this study we faced with some limitations, either related to the data and specifications of the databases that we used, or because of the study design and methodologies that we adopted.

It should be noted that for all databases the primary aim of data collection is patient management and not medical research. No single European data source contains all the information required in this study. This had several implications for this study. As we used retrospectively collected data from electronic health records (EHRs), some common limitations when using such data, e.g., misclassification bias or confounding, may still be pertained to this study. *Misclassification of exposure* might happen when there is an erroneous measurement and classification of drug exposure among the comparison groups in a pharmacoepidemiological study.³⁶ In some databases, such as CPRD, we had only GPs prescription information of valproates available, and in some other databases, such as PHARMO and ARS Tuscany we had dispensing information of valproates available. Also, CPRD and BIFAP do not capture outpatient specialist prescriptions, which may result in incomplete information on alternatives to valproates. Prescribing or dispensing information are 1 or 2 steps behind the actual drug use by patients, respectively. Thus, factors such as dispensing of the prescribed medication (in case of having access to prescriptions only), and adherence to medication can influence the true ascertainment of drug use by patients. Moreover, we have checked the missingness rates of various prescriptions and/or dispensings in our quality controls, as well as considering the discontinuation of valproates, which might be due to a switch.

Another potential limitation in our study was *misclassification of outcome*, especially in case of correct ascertainment of pregnancy records. This is usually a more difficult one to capture with EHRs than other disease outcomes, as gestational age is usually not available, and it can depend on different pregnancy-related covariates in the database such as pregnancy planning, prenatal visits, any related laboratory or imaging result, and delivery outcome. To minimise any issues with misclassification of pregnancy records, we used an adapted version of a previously validated algorithm, called "Matcho algorithm".²⁷ Through a series of sequential steps, this algorithm determines the date of pregnancy outcome (e.g., live birth, stillbirth, ectopic pregnancy, and abortion), and also the start date of a pregnancy episode using a hierarchy of pregnancy start markers, including last menstrual period date, gestational age record date, nuchal ultrasound record date, alpha fetoprotein test record date, and urine pregnancy record date. It is worth mentioning that a considerable number of concurrent pregnancies with valproate exposure in some databases were with the quality colour code red (see **Annex 9**), which might mean an abortion and thus fewer actual counts of live births who were in real danger of a teratogenic risk by the drug. Moreover, misclassification of other outcomes such as ADRs might have happened. Mild cases of nausea and tremor might not be recorded, although in such mild cases we do not expect the symptoms to lead to discontinuation. The same issue was applicable to indications of valproate use, as despite using proxy indicators from each database, a vast majority of indications in stratified analyses of incident and prevalent use was "unknown" across databases.

Another limitation was the lack of available information on over-the-counter contraceptives, which are not captured in any of the databases. Therefore, our ability to capture oral contraceptive use (especially in Italy) was limited, and records of barrier methods were not available. This might have resulted in an underestimation of the proportion of valproate episodes that meet the criteria for adequate contraceptive coverage. However, since the error was likely to be equal over time, it may have led to less power to detect a difference but not a differential error. The similar story applies to pregnancy testing, where we could not retrieve any data from DNR, ARS, PHARMO and CPRD, and very limited data from BIFAP, as most of the pregnancy tests were possibly over-the-counter without proper recording in the EHD. Due to this major limitation, it was not possible to conduct the planned analyses for the first sub-objective of Objective 2.

Another challenge was the lack of free-text information available from the different sources, leaving us reliant on records of products and diagnoses. This has mainly limited our ability to determine the reasons for valproate discontinuation. While discussions of pregnancy wish may have been recorded by general practitioners, this study must rely on folic acid prescriptions as a proxy for pregnancy wish, which may have low sensitivity.

The occurrence of the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic was another obstacle in conducting this research. When the time of implementation of EU RMMs for pregnancy prevention

with valproate use was almost the second half of 2018 in all different participating countries, the time afterwards to capture data on post-intervention period was critical. With the beginning of COVID-19 pandemic in December 2019, almost all countries went into periods of partial or full lockdown in 2020, which certainly affected not only the healthcare resources, but also access to health services, and patients' behaviour, especially their adherence with repeated prescriptions. This has also brought us practical difficulties in accessing data from various databases, due to concurrent COVID-19 projects and slower approval and releasing of data by competent authorities. This was particularly an issue with DNR. To overcome this issue, we defined some sensitivity analyses only for the COVID-19 period or some other excluding it, with the aim to have the analyses and results until the beginning of COVID-19 pandemic with estimates free of any effect from it. As an alternative to the data from Denmark originally requested, an existing data set of drug utilisation data was re-purposed to enable several analyses to still be performed.

11.4.4. Limitations related to methodology

One of the important limitations that we had in this study by using an ITS analysis model was not having equally spaced intervals before and after the intervention. Due to practical reasons and by design, the considered follow-up time before implementing the intervention was much longer (2010-2018) compared with the time after the intervention (2018-2020). The shorter follow-up time after the intervention has become even shorter when the COVID-19 pandemic started in December 2019, as mentioned above, making the assessments even more difficult. This might have reduced our ability to establish a sound trend in medication use in a shorter follow-up time after the intervention. However, as we used large nationwide databases and extracted several observation periods in a monthly manner, we were able to compensate this limitation to some extent.

Several methodological points need to be considered when conducting a study with an ITS analysis design.³³ "Autocorrelation" refers to the consecutive dependence of exposure or outcome events during the follow-up, in a way that those closer to each other are more similar than those that are further apart. "Non-stationarity" denotes to an underlying trend in the exposure or outcome event, which is unrelated to the intervention of interest, but can affect any found result from the intervention. Furthermore "seasonality" means any temporal fluctuation in the trend of medication or vaccine use, for example, which can confound the impact of intervention of interest on the trend changes. The relatively long follow-up time before implementing the intervention and our analysis model, i.e., segmented Poisson regression analysis, have helped us to identify any autocorrelation or non-stationary data among our valproate users, thus minimising any impact from these on the final results. Furthermore, our exposure drug, i.e., valproate, is not a good candidate to have seasonal fluctuation in its use.

The other potential issue when using an ITS analysis model could be not having a clear intervention time point, or any possible lag period afterwards. The PPP was not a clearly defined intervention. The staggered implementation across Europe made it challenging to assess the impact of the PPP on the various outcomes under study. An inability to incorporate the exact time point of the intervention in the ITS model, especially with multiple centres that had slightly different time of implementation of the intervention, could have led to mingling of pre- and post-intervention periods and flawed results. As it was not possible to fully establish precise dates of implementation in each of the countries due to variation at the regional and practice levels, we decided to model an implementation period of 6 months for the ITS analyses, which aimed to broadly capture the stepwise implementation. We also used a segmented Poisson regression analysis that also considered a term for the implementation period. Nonetheless, we are aware that our decision on the implementation period might have influenced the results of the ITS analysis.

A practical limitation in the estimation of treatment switching is that the definition of treatment switching used in this study did not distinguish between true switching and concomitant use of other medicines with an indication for epilepsy, bipolar disorder or migraine. This may have led to an

overestimation of the incidence of switching. By counting prescriptions or dispensings that occurred during the 90-day discontinuation period of valproate, true switches were more likely detected during those periods.

As another potential limitation in this study, one can think of any unmeasured time-varying confounder that has affected our outcome of interest or target population over time, especially when we did not have any control group or comparison outcome.³⁴ For example, we were not aware of any major extraneous changes in societal habits or beliefs regarding pregnancy testing or contraception, nor changes in regional policies on reimbursement of pregnancy testing or contraception, over the study period. This is usually an obstacle when conducting a quasi-experimental design, such as an ITS analysis, to study the effect of an intervention in a single study population without any comparable control group.³⁴ However, stratifying our target population by age, or producing multiple results in different countries with different set of plausible unmeasured confounders and the ultimate pooling of the results,³⁷ could have helped to reduce an effect from this. Thus, our conclusions particularly for Objective 5 was based on a combination of descriptive results and hypothesis testing.

12. Conclusions

We conclude there was a small impact of the 2018 RMMs on valproate use and prescribing in the studied European countries/regions, considering a declining trend in utilisation patterns of valproates among women of childbearing potential since 2010 and after the implementation of 2018 RMMs in Europe, no increasing trend in compliant valproate prescriptions/ dispensings with a contraceptive coverage, a significant increase in switching rates from valproates to alternative medications only in few regions, and declining rates of concurrent pregnancy events with valproate exposure in most countries/regions. This message is in keeping with the limitations of our study, as not all PPP elements could be studied, the included databases had important limitations, and the study period after 2018 intervention was rather short. A clearer picture of the appropriate implementation of RMMs on valproate use in Europe can only be understood when other studies, which are currently evaluating various other aspects of PPP implementation on valproate utilisation, would have been taken into account.

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Annex 1. List of stand-alone documents

Number	Date	Title
Annex 2	03 December 2021	Study protocol (amended), Version 1.1, EUPAS31001
Annex 3	25 February 2022	Data source-specific algorithms for study variables
Annex 4	25 February 2022	Statistical analysis plan for ascertainment of start and end of pregnancies and code list
Annex 5	25 February 2022	List of codes (diagnosis, treatment, procedure, medical observation and processed free text) used in the study
Annex 6	25 February 2022	Extract, Transformation, Loading (ETL) conversion template for DAPs
Annex 7	23 December 2021	Quality control (level 1-3 check) sheets used for evaluating the data quality
Annex 8	25 February 2022	Review and benchmarking documents used for internal and external validation of the study results
Annex 9	11 May 2022	ZIP file containing complete tables of counts and rates for each objective and data source, including the results of sensitivity and stratified analyses

Signature

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